

D 2.2 & D2.3 – Report on survey results and theoretical framework

WP2 – Exploring gendered intersectional patterns in citizen's behaviours and orientations towards energy transition

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Report on survey results and theoretical framework

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<i>Abstract</i>	This report explores intersectional patterns in energy consumption and citizenship across six European and four Sub-Saharan countries. Using machine learning, it identifies how gender, socio-economic status, and caregiving shape energy access, political efficacy, and sustainability capability. Results show that while gender alone has limited impact, intersecting inequalities significantly influence energy marginalization. In the Global South, affordability and infrastructure drive exclusion, whereas in the Global North, social and technical factors interact more equally. The findings highlight the need for targeted, equity-focused energy policies to ensure a just transition.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY: UNDERSTANDING THE DIVERSITY OF ENERGY TRANSITION

The energy transition has many faces. People vary in their technological affinity, education, financial resources, values, and life circumstances. This diversity makes it challenging to design smart policies from local to supranational level that effectively expand access to affordable clean energy while ensuring fair participation for all.

This report makes the diversity of energy systems in the EU and Sub-Saharan Africa tangible—highlighting the diversity of energy consumers, the diversity of citizens, and the barriers they face in fully participating in energy systems. Our focus is on how **gender** intersects with other social characteristics and the technical aspects of energy consumption. By identifying intersectional patterns in energy access and participation, we aim to contribute to the development of smarter, more demand-driven energy transition policies.

- With regards to extreme experiences of energy marginalization, urbanity and education are key predictors in Global South, while in Global North, age and household structure play a relatively greater role. Caregiving responsibilities are significant in both regions, with mixed effects—they enhance energy political self-efficacy, increase the likelihood of experiencing eco-anxiety, and limit sustainability capability.

Our core assumption is that participating in energy systems—whether as consumers, prosumers, or in energy policymaking—requires access to resources. **These resources stem from financial, social, and cultural capital, which are not distributed equally across gender.** The gender pay gap, gender care gap, and early socialisation into different degrees of technology interests all contribute to gendered inequalities in energy access and engagement.

Key Insights from This Report

- Five different types of experiences of energy marginalisation have been analysed. A country-level comparison of (1) energy poverty, (2) sustainability capability, (3) energy political self-efficacy, (4) (co-)ownership of renewable energy, and (5) eco-anxiety shows that considerable gender differences emerge regarding energy political self-efficacy. For the other types **gender** plays a relatively minor role.
- In Global South, energy marginalisation is primarily shaped by energy availability and affordability, whereas in the Global North, technical and social factors are equally important.

This report extends this gender perspective by comparing patterns across the EU (Global North) and Sub-Saharan Africa (Global South) to highlight how regional differences shape energy participation.

A truly inclusive and **gender-sensitive** energy transition policy must go beyond one-size-fits-all regulations and develop targeted, practical measures that address the specific barriers faced by different consumer groups.

As part of the two public reports on the gEneSys citizen dataset, this report provides an exploratory overview of the data, discussing its theoretical and practical implications. A follow-up report will focus on in-depth case studies, offering insights into the lived experiences of the people behind these data.

OBJECTIVES OF THE WORK PACKAGE AND THE REPORT

Who Are the Disadvantaged of the Current Energy System?

This report is based on the idea that energy consumption and energy citizenship require various forms of capital—such as financial, educational, or social resources. These resources are not equally distributed across society. As a result, some groups are excluded from the benefits of the energy system. The report examines these patterns in the EU and Sub-Saharan Africa, showing how systemic inequalities leave certain groups disadvantaged in terms of access, participation, and opportunities. The question of the place of gender in these systemic inequalities plays a central role in this report's considerations.

The European Union is pursuing the goal of an ecologically sustainable and socially just energy transition. However, the acceptance and successful implementation of such an unprecedented systemic transformation of the energy system depends largely on the consent and behaviour of citizens. Despite laudable efforts in recent years towards greater equity in the energy system, gender, and intersectional inequalities in terms of access to resources, education, employment, and participation in the political process remain widespread, largely affecting the acceptance of the global energy transition.

These inequality aspects have often been neglected in previous research on the energy transition (Herbert et al. 2020). This leaves a considerable knowledge gap that urgently needs to be filled in order to promote a more equitable and inclusive energy policy.

Work package (WP) 2 of the gEneSys project aims to establish a theoretical understanding of the socio-cultural influences on achieving the energy transition and creating an equitable energy transition. It draws on and supplements the results of WP1 by improving the understanding of intersectional gender aspects in the energy sector. In principle, WP2 identifies new evidence on two main dimensions: first, sociodemographic gender-related differences in behaviours, values, and orientations of citizens towards the energy transition and second, intersectional gender injustice issues in energy transitions.

This report combines the original deliverables 2.2 and 2.3. The main reason for combining the two originally planned reports was changes in the project schedule due to the longer than planned ethics review of the survey project reported here.

The aim of this report is to present the results of exploratory data analyses in which the collected data is searched for intersectional patterns regarding energy consumption and energy citizenship (the latter defined as an active engagement related to the energy use of a citizen or their community). These patterns, in which the

gender category is prioritised, are discussed and interpreted. The results of the systematic literature reviews conducted as part of gEneSys (Cellini et al. 2025) and background discussions with scientific experts were used for this purpose.

The result of the report is a theoretical framework for explaining the phenomena of energy marginalisation. In order to make this theoretical framework as tangible and vivid as possible for science communication, a series of personas are derived at the end of the report, which describe extreme real types in the context of energy consumption and energy citizenship, taking gender aspects into account. In the further research process, the theoretical framework will be applied to specific case studies and thus further optimised.

THEORETICAL ASSUMPTIONS

Intersectionality is a concept that is attracting increasing interest in energy research. This section describes examples of intersectional energy studies and summarises the current state of research. It then introduces the central concepts of this report (such as the idea of the Resource Man, the Capability Approach, or Capital Theory), which are continuously taken up in the report and are key to its understanding.

State of research on intersectionality and the energy system

To better understand the effects of energy transitions, scholars emphasize the importance of applying intersectional feminist theories in energy policy making. These theories focus on the interconnected systems of oppression and the resulting inequalities faced by individuals who belong to multiple marginalized and disadvantaged social groups. This intersectional perspective highlights that the repercussions of energy injustices extend beyond gender alone, intertwining with social status, race, ethnicity, and other dimensions (Crenshaw 1989, 1997; Fathallah and Pyakurel 2020; Winther et al. 2020).

By using this lens, it becomes possible to conduct a comprehensive examination of power dynamics and justice in the decision-making processes related to energy and climate change. More precisely, intersectionality theory is seen as a way to enrich or even surpass traditional, often Western-centric, notions of justice by incorporating perspectives from feminist, anti-racist, Indigenous, and postcolonial justice theories (Rainard et al. 2025).

With growing recognition of their importance in analysing complex social inequalities, intersectional studies are gradually gaining traction in research related to energy systems. For example, in their study on green grabbing and ejido privatization in Zacatecas, Mexico, Vázquez-García and Sosa-Capistrán (2021) describe intersectional effects by examining the dynamics within green grabbing and land privatization focusing on the ways in which gender, class, and ethnicity intersect to shape the experiences of women. Ngarava et al. (2022) explore how energy poverty is experienced differently across gender and ethnic lines in South Africa, adopting an intersectional lens to examine these disparities. It highlights how women, particularly from marginalized ethnic groups, are disproportionately affected by energy poverty due to overlapping factors such as gender roles, economic marginalization, and social exclusion.

Similarly, Stock (2021) explores how the electricity and water infrastructures in the Gujarat Solar Park in India exacerbate existing social inequalities. By applying an intersectional lens, the study highlights how marginalized communities, particularly in terms of gender, class, and ethnicity, experience unequal access to resources and face disproportionate impacts from energy and water policies.

Further, Corsi et al. (2021) explored how gender and maternal roles intersect to affect the self-efficacy of post-graduate students in renewable energy programs in Argentinian and Guatemalan universities. They point out the compounded challenges faced by women with maternal responsibilities, suggesting that their experiences in these academic programs are influenced not only by gender but also by family dynamics.

Martinez-Reyes et al. (2025) conducted research on intersectional energy justice with a focus on Rotterdam, Netherlands. She observed how factors such as gender, socio-economic status, household insulation quality, property rights, as well as social factors like language and time spent at home, and others such as interest in, knowledge of, and awareness about energy policies intersect to affect individuals' exposure to the benefits and burdens of energy transitions. The authors identified five groups most prone to vulnerability: single parents, unemployed individuals, the elderly, students, and immigrants. By highlighting these intersecting dimensions, the paper reveals which groups are disproportionately impacted by energy policies, offering a more nuanced understanding of energy justice.

Taken together, these studies make it clear that energy transitions and energy justice policies must go beyond economic affordability and infrastructure improvements. Instead, they must account for the layered disadvantages faced by marginalized groups and develop targeted, context-specific interventions. Without such an approach, energy policies risk reinforcing existing inequalities rather than alleviating them. The exemplary studies convey that an intersectional lens is thus not only beneficial but essential for designing fair and effective energy policies that ensure equitable access to energy resources and benefits.

However, while intersectionality informed frameworks are gaining traction in energy research, their integration into discussions on equity, justice, and intersectionality is still in its early stages, particularly with regard to how issues are defined, strategies are carried out, and the pathways envisioned for a just transition to a fossil fuel-free future (Cannon and Chu 2021).

According to a literature review on the nexus of energy and gender carried out by Cellini et al. (2025), a significant portion of research exploring the intersection of gender and energy fails to adopt an intersectional approach, often treating women as a homogeneous group and overlooking the complexities of their diverse social identities and experiences. Moreover, the intersectional studies highlighted above are predominantly qualitative in nature and concentrate on specific regional contexts or small case studies. Accordingly, there is a noticeable gap in the existing literature when it comes to large-scale, systematic intersectional research that comprehensively examines energy transitions on a broader scale. Such studies, which would integrate multiple dimensions of inequality and address a wider range of geographical

and socio-political settings, are currently underrepresented not to say completely missing in the field.

Admittedly, integrating intersectionality into research is quite complicated on a practical level, and the energy justice literature still lacks concrete strategies for its application. Using intersectionality in research requires a nuanced understanding of its foundational principles, which must be carefully applied throughout the research process (Rainard et al. 2025).

Against this background, we seek to undertake a comprehensive and systematic exploration of robust intersectional patterns that relate to energy poverty, justice factors, and energy behaviours. Through this research, we aim to uncover the complex interactions between various social dimensions such as gender, socio-economic status, ethnicity, and other factors that influence individuals' experiences with energy access and use, as well as their engagement with energy policies and practices.

Introducing Basic terms and concept

The exploratory intersectional analyses presented in this report is based on the initial structural model presented in the conceptual framework report (D2.1) and on the methodological approaches of energy justice and intersectional research. These frameworks provide a structured foundation for examining the complexities of social inequalities within the energy sector. In this section, we introduce key concepts that serve as guiding principles for our analyses and interpretations, ensuring a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the findings presented in this report.

A key foundation of the analysis is the principle that energy systems can be seen as socio-technical systems—complex networks that integrate both technical infrastructure and social components such as consumer behaviour, policy frameworks, and community acceptance (Ainley, 2019; Interaction Design Foundation - IxDF, 2015). They are designed with consumers in mind (IxDF, 2015) and must adapt to changes in technology, policy, and societal values (IxDF, 2015; Research Institute for Sustainability, 2019).

This framework offers a lens through which we can examine the dynamic interplay between technical components, social structures, and environmental factors, operating on the fundamental premise that disparities between groups arise not only from differences in behaviour but also from unequal access to energy infrastructure. The advantages of this approach are manifold: it fosters greater energy justice by addressing energy poverty and unequal access (Ainley, 2019), supports more sustainable energy transitions (Ainley, 2019; Rohracher, 2018), and enhances decision-making through models that integrate socio-technical considerations (Amin et al., 2024; Research Institute for Sustainability, 2019). In essence, this holistic perspective strives

to strike a balance between technical efficiency, social equity, and long-term sustainability.

Grounded in this framework, our core assumption is that an individual's capability for participation in the energy system depends on the access to specific individual resources. In an article of Strengers (2014) the concept of the Resource Man was introduced. The concept describes a (smart) energy consumer who is an efficient, tech-savvy and often male energy user. Strenger emphasizes that this kind of hyper-competent energy user rarely exists in reality – but represents the typical persona whom designers of energy systems are optimising products and services for. She then argues that the resource man persona oversimplifies households' life by focusing solely on measurable metrics (e.g. kilowatt hours and cost) whilst neglecting elements like comfort and convenience. Strenger advocates for an understanding of energy management that embraces the varied realities of daily life and supports alternative, low energy lifestyles.

This basic idea that participation in energy requires individual resources leads to the question which kind of resources are related to which kind of energy-related participation or marginalisation experiences. One possible answer to this can be found in Bourdieu's (2010) meanwhile classical capital theory.

Bourdieu introduced the capital theory which expands the concept of capital beyond just economic resources to include various forms of assets that individuals accumulate and use to gain social power. There are three forms of capital (economic, cultural and social), as defined in table 1.

Table 1: Types of capital according to Bourdieu (2010).

Economic Capital	Cultural Capital	Social Capital
Capital that is directly transformable into money. This kind of capital is the easiest to convert into other forms.	Includes education, knowledge and cultural competences that influence social positions and opportunities in an incorporated, objectified or institutionalized form.	Social networks, relationships and obligations that connect people and groups. Social capital gives people access to resources and support within a social group.

Different forms of capital interact and convert into one another, influencing social position and mobility. A person with significant cultural capital can leverage it into economic gains or build networks through social capital, demonstrating that social inequity is maintained not only by economic differences but also by the unequal distribution of these capitals.

Strenger's (2014) concept of the Resource Man aligns with Bourdieu's (2010) capital theory, showing how various capital sources equip individuals with distinct resources.

According to cultural capital theory, the Resource Man possesses technical literacy, education, and energy management skills that enable effective use of smart energy technologies, while those lacking these assets may struggle.

Additionally, the Resource Man requires substantial economic capital to access and maintain these systems. Social capital also plays a crucial role, as being embedded in rich networks facilitates the sharing of energy management practices—sometimes reflecting gendered responsibilities such as household energy management. In this way, the interplay of cultural, economic, and social capital not only shapes the ideal of the smart energy consumer but also reinforces existing social hierarchies.

The concept of energy justice shapes the here applied understanding of energy marginalization offering a framework to evaluate the fairness and equity of energy systems. In general, energy justice encompasses three core principles: distributive justice, procedural justice, and justice in recognition (Jenkins et al., 2016, 2021; Sovacool and Dworkin, 2015). These principles are particularly useful when assessing the impacts of energy transitions and policies on various communities, ensuring that they benefit fairly from energy services while minimizing harm. The concept of energy justice inspired our selection of outcomes to be analysed. For example, with energy political self-efficacy we consider an aspect of procedural justice or justice in recognition, with the (co-)ownership of renewable energy systems an aspect of distributive justice or with eco-anxiety an aspect of justice in recognition.

Furthermore, tackling energy injustice requires an equitable approach to energy policy that prioritizes the diverse needs and rights of all communities today and in the future. This is why, inspired by Day et al. (2016), this report also takes up the capability approach to better understand the complexities around energy justice. In general, the capability approach is a theoretical framework for evaluating human well-being and social arrangements being developed by Sen (1985) and Nussbaum (2010). The approach lays its focus on two different normative claims:

- 1) The freedom to achieve well-being is of primary moral importance.
- 2) This freedom should be understood in terms of people's capabilities, which are their real opportunities to do and be what they have reason to value.

The capability approach emphasizes what people can actually do and be—focusing on valued achievements (functioning) and the freedoms or opportunities (capabilities) to achieve them, while considering the personal, social, and environmental factors that influence how resources are converted into these functioning. Recognizing human diversity, this approach shifts the focus from mere resource provision to actual well-being.

Applied to the energy sector, it reframes energy poverty as a form of capability deprivation, where inadequate or unaffordable energy services prevent individuals from achieving essential life goals such as health, education, and social or political participation (Day et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2021; Melin et al., 2021). It categorizes energy needs into biological (e.g., heating), intellectual/emotional (e.g., education via electricity), and social/political dimensions (e.g., participation in decision-making), providing a framework for evaluating policies based on their ability to enhance these capabilities rather than just increasing resource availability.

Additionally, this report extends the capability approach to explore another dimension of energy marginalization: the capability for sustainable and energy-efficient behaviour. This perspective considers whether individuals and communities have the opportunities and freedoms to adopt energy-efficient practices and make sustainable energy choices. By incorporating this dimension, the report aims to measure not only access to energy but also the capacity to engage in energy behaviours that support long-term well-being.

Taken together, the concepts of the Resource Man, of capital theory, energy justice, and capability theory used here contribute to a comprehensive assessment of energy marginalization, examining its various manifestations and dimensions. By drawing on these theoretical perspectives, the report seeks to offer a nuanced understanding of the ways in which energy marginalization unfolds and the multiple factors that influence its impact on different communities. Each of these concepts plays a crucial role in framing the issue and guiding the assessment of how energy systems can be more equitable and inclusive.

METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodological approach used for the intersectional exploratory analyses of this report. It explains the selection of countries studied and the operationalization of energy marginalization using five distinct outcome variables. Additionally, it introduces two predictive models: an intersectional model and a socio-technical model. The section also provides details on the technical aspects of the survey and the analyses conducted.

Country selection

The survey was set to take place across six European countries and four Sub-Saharan countries, involving around 3,000 participants in each country and totalling 30,000 participants overall. The selected countries for the survey were chosen to reflect a diverse mix of prosperity levels, energy systems and welfare systems – and in terms of private energy consumption of relevance, climate zones. Care was also taken to cover countries with as large a population as possible in order to be able to derive (within limits) representative insights for the highest possible proportion of citizens in the regions surveyed within the scope of the project.

Why compare the EU and Sub-Saharan Africa?

The data collection and comparison of the EU and Sub-Saharan Africa were driven by the gEneSys project design, which aims to foster intercontinental collaboration on Sustainable Development Goal 7, "Affordable and Clean Energy," in both research and policy. Due to considerable differences in wealth and climate, direct comparisons between the two regions are often impractical. Therefore, this report conducts separate analyses for the Global North (EU states) and the Global South (Sub-Saharan states). Comparing these distinct analyses provides a more comprehensive perspective on global experiences of energy marginalization.

In part, the selection of countries was also based on organisational and economic considerations, as not every survey service provider has access to high-quality survey panels in every country in Sub-Saharan Africa, for example, or such access would be associated with high costs. The survey countries are listed in table 2.

Table 2: Countries to be surveyed in Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa.

Global North (European Union)	Global South (Sub-Saharan Africa)
France	Kenya
Germany	Nigeria
Italy	Uganda
Poland	South Africa
Portugal	
Sweden	

We refer to the EU and Sub-Saharan countries analysed below as the Global North and South. This terminology conveys our assumption that, despite their regional focus, the respective country groups can provide insights into typical forms of energy marginalisation for the groups of countries belonging to the Global North and the Global South as a whole.

Table 3 provides a concise overview of the countries studied, based on a range of key statistical indicators. The data highlight a clear wealth disparity between the countries categorized as part of the Global North and Global South, as reflected in GNI per capita and electricity access. However, when considering the included Gender Equality Index, no clearly patterned differences between the North and South are observed.

Table 3: Introductory key data of the surveyed countries (World Bank 2023a; United Nations, 2024; World Bank, 2023b; World Bank 2022; World Economic Forum, 2024; Statistisches Bundesamt, 2021).

	Italy	Germany	France	Poland	Portugal	Sweden	South Africa	Kenya	Nigeria	Uganda
Population	59 M	84.1 M	68 M	37.6 M	10.4 M	10.5 M	59.9 M	54.0 M	218.5 M	47.3 M
Median age of population	47,8	45,3	42,1	41,8	46,6	40,1	28,5	19,8	17,9	16,7
Part of population living in urban areas	72%	78%	82%	60%	68%	89%	69%	30%	54%	27%
Electricity Access	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	86.5%	76.0%	60.5%	47.1%
Gender Equality Index	70%	81%	76%	72%	77%	81%	78%	71%	64%	71%
GNI per capita	35,710 \$	51,040 \$	43,880 \$	16,670 \$	23,730 \$	58,890 \$	6,440 \$	2,010 \$	2,100 \$	840 \$

The comparison of the key metrics also reveals strong variation within both the North and South group. For instance, South Africa's GNI per capita is more than seven times that of Uganda, while Sweden's GNI per capita is over three times higher than Poland's. The proportion of the population living in urban areas in Poland is again much lower than in the other northern states. It is more comparable to the average urbanisation level of South Africa and Nigeria, while Kenya and Uganda have the lowest urbanisation levels.

As explained in the following section, for some parts of the analyses the collected data were weighted to be representative for each country. This approach allows the dataset to provide representative insights into countries that together account for

more than half of the EU's population and one-third of Sub-Saharan Africa's population.¹

Description of the survey procedure

On behalf of the Center for Responsible Research and Innovation at the Fraunhofer IAO, the survey service provider Ipsos conducted a representative survey of the population in the ten target countries. The target population for Poland, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa and Uganda were people aged 18 to 65 who are resident in the respective countries and have access to the internet. In France, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Sweden the target population were people aged 18 to 75 who are resident in the respective countries and have access to the internet.

The sample was drawn from the Ipsos Online Panels by quota selection according to the characteristics age, gender, region (NUTS 2 in general, NUTS1 in France and Germany) and education in France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Sweden and South Africa and the characteristics of gender and age in Kenya, Nigeria and Uganda. These central sociodemographic data had been pre-defined so that Ipsos could directly target respondents via invitation email in order to achieve a representative distribution of these features. With more than 4.5 million panellists in 43 countries, Ipsos panels cover all major markets in Europe, North and South America, South-east Asia, the Middle East and North Africa.

The final questionnaire was provided by Fraunhofer IAO in English and Ipsos coordinated the translation of the questionnaire into all other country languages (see table 4 below).

Table 4: Overview of languages

Country	Languages
France	French
Germany	German
Italy	Italian
Poland	Polish
Portugal	Portuguese
Sweden	Swedish
Kenya	English, Swahili
Nigeria	English, Hausa, Yoruba
South Africa	English, Afrikaans
Uganda	English, Luganda, Swahili

The fieldwork for the quantitative online interviews took place between October 14, 2024 and January 21, 2025. A total of 30,001 interviews was achieved.

Important: To comply with the time limits for the reporting obligations, a preliminary version of the data set was used for this report. All countries except Uganda are

¹ Own estimation based on population data of the World Bank Group: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL>, accessed on 8 January 2025.

already represented in this dataset with 3000 cases. Uganda comprises 2507 cases. In the final data set, 492 additional cases were collected for France, Italy and Uganda in particular in order to arrive at the desired total number of 30,000 cases.

Incentives that panellists received for participating in surveys depend on the country, the duration of the survey and the complexity of the survey. In addition to sweepstakes, Ipsos uses a point system to provide incentives to panellists. Point systems are recognized as an adequate approach to conducting online market research, as they are considered a neutral system that does not introduce any bias in terms of participation from certain groups of people. The accumulated points can be exchanged by panellists for a range of rewards on a website set up specifically for this purpose. For a 25 minutes survey, panellists are awarded 150 points.

Ipsos ensures respondent quality through multiple verification measures, including double opt-in, geographic validation, proxy detection, CAPTCHA codes, and digital fingerprinting. Panellists follow strict rules to prevent excessive survey participation and maintain data reliability.

To ensure engagement, Ipsos monitors response behaviour in real time using self-adjusting algorithms. Respondents displaying inattentive behaviour are automatically removed. Speeding detection identifies respondents completing surveys more than twice as fast as the median and removes them in real time. Straight-lining detection flags respondents who provide identical answers across grid questions, particularly when opposite statements require varied responses.

Both processes run automatically, adjusting dynamically based on live survey behaviour. Repeat offenders are deactivated. After fieldwork, the data was weighted in multiple stages. Demographic adjustments were made to align the sample with official statistics, compensating for normal fluctuations.

Quotas for gender, age, region, and education were used in most countries, while in Kenya, Nigeria, and Uganda, only gender and age were considered. Target figures were sourced from Eurostat (2022) and other official statistics.

Ipsos applied IPF weighting (Iterative Proportional Fitting), adjusting the sample iteratively to match target distributions. Weighting factors were recalculated until all variables aligned with the specified targets. Weighting efficiencies varied across countries (see table 5). The calculated weightings were used in particular for the country wise gender gaps of the individual outcomes presented in this report.

Table 5: Weighting efficiency.

Country	Weighting efficiency
France	79,5%
Germany	77,5%
Italy	67,9%
Poland	93,7%
Portugal	67,6%
Sweden	82,9%
Kenya	72,2%
Nigeria	84,8%
South Africa	87,8%
Uganda	59,2%

Outcome Variables: from subjective energy poverty to eco-anxiety

The aim of this report is to examine the relationship between an individual's socio-demographic characteristics and the technical aspects of their energy use, focusing on those who have experienced marginalisation in energy consumption and energy citizenship. To provide a comprehensive understanding of energy marginalisation, the phenomenon has been divided into five subcategories. Based on the capital theory introduced earlier, it is hypothesised that experiences of marginalisation in these five areas are likely influenced by varying levels of, for example, financial, social, or educational capital.

One challenge in operationalising the concept of energy marginalisation was the need for the formulated items to exhibit high universality. This meant that the survey items had to be designed in a way that made them easy and quick to answer for respondents, regardless of their country, educational background, or level of experience with energy marginalisation. As a result, the ability to draw extensively on validated questionnaire items from previous studies was strongly limited, as these - if available at all - were often developed within the framework of non-exploratory research designs or under certain regional contextual conditions.

Specifically, the following aspects of energy marginalisation were operationalised:

- The **Energy Poverty Index** is a compilation of self-developed questionnaire items that, when taken together, measure the believe of a person to which extent their household has access to affordable, reliable and non-harmful energy. The higher the index value, the better the access.
- The **Energy political Self-efficacy Index (EPSEI)** measures the extent to which a person believes that they can express a competent opinion on energy policy and the extent to which politicians are interested in energy policy opinions. The higher the index value, the better the energy political self-efficacy.

- **(Co-)ownership of renewable energy production installation or storage facility** measures if a person confirmed to be an owner or co-owner of a renewable energy production installation or storage facility. The variable can take the values "Renewable energy (co-)ownership" (9.9%), "Other ownership" (12.2%), or "No energy ownership" (73.6%). The percentages refer to the proportion of the sample size that falls into each category. The total sample for this variable consists of $n=28,258$.
- The **Energy Sustainability Capability Index (ESCI)** measures a person's self-assessed ability to organise their own energy consumption efficiently and sustainably. The higher the index, the higher this perceived capability. The index items are taken from a comprehensive self-developed questionnaire which is based on the capability approach developed by Nussbaum (2000).²
- The **Eco Anxiety Index** measures the extent to which a person experiences a feeling of psychological stress due to the perception of environmental degradation. The higher the index, the more pronounced this feeling.

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for the calculated index scores as well as the descriptive statistics for the individual items that make up these indices. In addition to means, scale ranges, standard deviations, and sample sizes, Cronbach's Alpha values are provided at the index level.

Cronbach's Alpha is a statistical measure used to assess the reliability or internal consistency of a test or questionnaire. It indicates how well the individual questions or items of a test align to measure the same construct. As general benchmarks, Cronbach's Alpha values between 0.7 and 0.9 are considered acceptable. A lower value suggests that the items forming an index may lack sufficient consistency and, therefore, may not reliably measure the same construct. Conversely, a value that is too high might indicate redundancy, as the items may be overly similar.

The calculated Cronbach's Alpha values in this study are all within an acceptable range, indicating that there is no statistical objection to combining the respective items into their four indices.

² By operationalizing the capability approach in the context of energy, we aim to transcend conventional measurements and explore the broader implications of energy-related disparities on individuals' fundamental capabilities and, consequently, their general welfare. By coupling quantitative data on energy availability, affordability, safety and reliability with an assessment of well-being through the capability lens, we aim to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the multifaceted dynamics between energy, justice, and citizens' overall flourishing.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics and Cronbach's Alpha Value (α) of the index variables and the corresponding index values.

Variable labels	Index name or item wording	Scale Minimum - Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
Energy Poverty Index ($\alpha = .797$)	I can financially afford the amount of energy and energy resources required to supply all areas of my household	1 - 7	4,98	1,939	28818
	Energy and energy resources are available to me in the amounts needed to supply my household.	1 - 7	5,59	1,742	28820
	My household's energy and energy resources supply is reliable without outages.	1 - 7	5,11	1,927	28834
	The energy use in my household does not cause any harm or risks to my health (including the sourcing of materials and energy generation).	1 - 7	5,76	1,605	27993
Energy political Self-efficacy Index (EPSEI) ($\alpha = .753$)	Politicians strive to keep in close touch with the people regarding energy issues.	1 - 5	2,54	1,322	28370
	Politicians care about what ordinary people think about energy issues.	1 - 5	2,46	1,312	28429
	I am good at understanding and addressing important political topics regarding Energy issues.	1 - 5	3,66	1,202	28313
	I have the confidence to take active part in a discussion about political topics regarding energy issues.	1 - 5	3,59	1,296	28369
Capability for energy efficient and sustainable behaviour index ($\alpha = .827$)	Are you able to make conscious choices about your Energy use in line with your values?	1 - 7	5,49	1,607	27716
	Are you able to optimize and manage your energy consumption in the most efficient way possible?	1 - 7	5,40	1,587	28075
	Do you feel competent about energy policies and regulations that may impact your energy choices?	1 - 7	4,57	1,865	27183
	Are you able to avoid unnecessary waste of energy in your household?	1 - 7	5,69	1,506	28533
	Are you able to engage in environmental and climate protection	1 - 7	5,06	1,777	27047
	Are you able to choose to use renewable energy sources (for cooking, heating, vehicle's fuel etc.)?	1 - 7	4,55	2,100	26878
	Are you able to choose environmentally friendly alternatives when you make purchasing decisions?	1 - 7	5,20	1,731	27717
Ecological Anxiety ($\alpha = .883$)	Thinking about environmental degradation makes it difficult for me to sleep or concentrate.	1 - 5	2,30	1,201	28642
	I find myself crying because of environmental degradation.	1 - 5	2,06	1,224	28655
	My concerns about environmental degradation makes it hard for me to have fun with my family or friends.	1 - 5	2,31	1,194	28551
	My concerns about environmental degradation interfere with my ability to get work or school assignments done.	1 - 5	2,18	1,213	28192
(Co-)ownership of renewable energy	Renewable energy (co-) ownership	0/1	-	-	2988
	Other ownership	0/1	-	-	3676
	No energy ownership	0/1	-	-	21742

The content validity of the outcomes is also analysed at the beginning of the results section. For this purpose, the four metric indices were correlated with the Personal Relative Deprivation Index (PRDI) according to Callan et al. (2011). The characteristics of the PRDI are shown in Table 7. An explanation of the PRDI is provided at the beginning of the results section.

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics and Cronbach’s Alpha Value of the index variables and the corresponding index values.

Variable labels	Index name or item wording	Scale Minimum - Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
Personal Relative Deprivation Index ($\alpha = .568$)	I feel deprived when I think about what I have, compared to what other people like me have.	1 - 7	3,54	2,03	28218
	I feel privileged compared to other people like me. (R)	1 - 7	4,07	1,97	28237
	I feel resentful when I see how prosperous other people like me seem to be.	1 - 7	3,11	2,05	28091
	When I compare what I have with what others like me have, I realize that I am quite well off. (R)	1 - 7	4,33	1,88	28318
	I feel dissatisfied with what I have compared to what other people like me have.	1 - 7	3,4	2,05	28368

Predictors: intersectional and sociotechnical predictors

The predictor variables used in this exploratory study can be divided into three categories: intersectional variables, technological variables and control variables. For the exploratory analyses, these variable sets were used in two different constellations—only the intersectional variables, or the intersectional variables with the technological variables.

Intersectional variables

At the heart of our study lies the conviction that gender plays a pivotal role in shaping experiences of participation and marginalisation and, moreover, exerts profound effects on environmental values, beliefs, and behaviour. However, it is essential to acknowledge that the experiences of women within the energy sector are remarkably diverse, contingent upon their multifaceted backgrounds. Women of colour, indigenous women, LGBTQIA+ women, disabled women, and those from various socio-economic backgrounds grapple with distinct challenges (Fathallah and Pyakurel 2020). This intersectional perspective highlights that the repercussions of energy injustices extend beyond gender alone, intertwining with social status, race, ethnicity, and other dimensions (Crenshaw 1989, 1997; Fathallah and Pyakurel 2020; Winther et al. 2020).

The so-called intersectional variables are shown in Table 8. These are primary social identities in the sense of social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Primary social identities are those social group affiliations (such as gender, ethnicity or religion) that play a central role in an individual's self-concept. They are often stable, anchored early in socialisation and have a lasting influence on thinking, behaviour and interactions with others - people do not consciously choose these characteristics or, if they do not identify with the identities ascribed to them, must make a strong effort to distinguish themselves (Loden & Rosener, 1990; Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Unjustified unequal treatment of these characteristics is generally contrary to the constitutional

principles of equality in the countries analysed and to Article 21 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

Care responsibility, relationship status, the type of living model in the household and the urbanity of the place of residence are not primary social identities. These identity characteristics are individualised. Nevertheless, they are integrated into the intersectional predictor model used here, as they are social categories that are antecedent to the specific form of energy consumption (people do not form their relationships according to the type of heating they prefer. However, people's heating consumption is affected by their relationship models and their place of residence). The inclusion of identity characteristics that describe a person's partnership model is in line with a broad understanding of the concept of intersectionality. Many studies have shown that gender often only leads to experiences of marginalisation in combination with care responsibility (Budig & England, 2001; Damaske, 2011; Hines, 2007).

The intersectional variables were measured using the Diversity Minimal Item Set (DiMIS), developed by Stadler et al. (2023). The DiMIS is a questionnaire which aims to standardise the measurement of identity characteristics that are potentially relevant to discrimination. To use the DiMIS for the study conducted, it was adapted in two key respects. Firstly, a simplified operationalisation of gender was used (male, female, self-ascription), as the manifold response options of the DiMIS regarding gender were not considered suitable for a broad-based citizen survey (e.g. self-classification as cis would presumably have shown strong distortions according to the respondents' level of education). Secondly, for legal reasons, sexual orientation was not asked in Nigeria, Uganda and Kenya and ethnicity was not asked in France.

In addition to the DiMIS items, an item measuring the subjectively perceived urbanity of the place of residence was also included. The item was developed in orientation to Brinkhof et al. (2022). Respondents were asked to indicate the urbanity of their place of residence on a scale from 1 ("tiny village in rural area") to 7 ("city centre of [biggest city of the corresponding country]").

Table 8: Margin (%) and sample size (%) of the intersectional predictor Variables with Variable Labels and item wording.

Variable labels	Item wording	Margin %	N
COUNTRY	1 – France	10,2	3000
	2 – Germany	10,2	3000
	3 – Italy	10,2	3000
	4 – Poland	10,2	3000
	5 – Portugal	10,2	3000
	6 – Sweden	10,2	3000
	7 – Kenya	10,2	3000
	8 – Nigeria	10,2	3000
	9 – Uganda	8,5	2507
	10 – South Africa	10,2	3001
Respondent Age	The mean score for "respondent Age" was M = 41,41 (SD = 15,01), based on a sample of N = 29507 participants.		

QS1 Regarding gender identity, which of the following options best describes how you think of yourself?³	1 - Female	49,3	14552
	2 - Male	50,7	14955
	98 - Don't know	0	0
	99 - Prefer not to answer	0	0
QG2_grid_2 Taking care of someone in need (caring for children, elders, partners in need, etc.)	The mean score for "Taking care of someone in need (caring for children, elders, partners in need, etc.)" was M = 6.73 (SD = 5.89), based on a sample of N = 9189 participants.		
QP6 1-9 Sexual orientation	1 - Heterosexual	85,8	1664
	2 - Asexual	1,4	313
	3 - Bisexual	3,9	841
	4 - Gay	1,8	404
	5 - Lesbian	0,8	169
	6 - Pansexual	0,7	147
	7 - Another sexual orientation, please specify:	1,1	234
	8 - Don't know	1,1	240
	9 - Prefer not to answer	3,4	744
QP12 Do you identify as a member of an ethnic minority or racialized group? A racialized group is a societal group which is affected by racism or discrimination. The racialization may be based on skin colour, origin, religion, language, etc.	1 - Yes	22,5	6628
	2 - No	70,6	20836
	98 - Don't know	4,4	1286
	99 - Prefer not to answer	2,6	757
QP13 What is your present religious identity or world view, if any?	1 - Buddhist	0,6	184
	2 - Christian	63,3	18681
	3 - Hindu	0,5	149
	4 - Jewish	0,4	115
	5 - Muslim	5,6	1660
	6 - Atheist (do not believe in God)	11,6	3418
	7 - Agnostic (not sure if there is a God)	4,6	1347
	8 - Another religion, please specify:	1,5	450
	9 - Nothing in particular	8,5	2520
	98 - Don't know	0,9	267
99 - Prefer not to answer	2,4	717	
QP14 Have you ever been told by a doctor or health care professional that you have depression, anxiety or other mental health problems?	1 - Yes	22,0	6492
	2 - No	74,9	22106
	98 - Don't know	1,5	457
	99 - Prefer not to answer	1,5	452
QP15 Do you consider yourself to have a disability?	1 - Yes	9,9	2920
	2 - No	87,5	25826
	98 - Don't know	1,6	478
	99 - Prefer not to answer	1,0	283
QP16 Do you have any chronic illness or longstanding health problem? By longstanding we mean illnesses or health problems, which have lasted, or are expected to last, for 6 months or more.	1 - Yes	26,4	7775
	2 - No	70,5	20796
	98 - Don't know	1,8	532
	99 - Prefer not to answer	1,4	404
QP21 What is your relationship status?	1 - Single	29,0	8512
	2 - Dating / In a relationship	14,0	4135
	3 - Married	40,9	12074
	4 - Co-Habiting	8,0	2375
	5 - Divorced / Separated	5,3	1566
	6 - Widowed	1,6	477
	7 - Other, please specify:	0,2	69

³ QS1 is a system variable of the survey service provider. All panel members are stored in its database with a range of mandatory metadata. The distribution of the survey invitation is then based on the specified characteristic quotas. As the gender variable used by the survey service provider is binary, there are no alternatively classified persons. However, in order to be able to make statements about ambiguous gender attributions, the survey also asked which sex was attributed to a person at birth. The following frequency distribution is shown here: Female = 14768 (49.2%), Male = 15090 (50.3%), Intersex = 38 (0.1%), Don't know = 52 (0.2%), Prefer not to answer = 105 (0.3%).

	98 - Don't know	0,2	72
	99 - Prefer not to answer	0,8	227
QP22 How do you live?	1 - Alone	18,3	5400
	2 - With Parent(s) / Sibling(s)	15,9	4697
	3 - With Partner	22,1	6412
	4 - With Partner and children	33,2	9792
	5 - With children	6,6	1933
	6 - With Friends / House-share	2,3	668
	7 - Other, please specify:	1,0	295
	98 - Don't know	0,1	39
	99 - Prefer not to answer	0,9	270
	QP28 Please indicate how urban your living environment is.	1 - Tiny village in rural area	7,8
2 -		5,5	1620
3 -		9,7	2780
4 -		15,5	4573
5 -		21,9	6464
6 -		17,9	5276
7 - Very urban, for example in the city centre		20,2	5954
98 - Don't know		0,9	264
99 - Prefer not to answer		0,9	271
QG0 Are you currently responsible for taking care of someone in need?		1 - I am currently responsible for taking care of someone in need.	17,1
	2 - I have been responsible for taking care of someone in the past.	23,5	6930
	3 - I have never been responsible for taking care of someone in need.	36,4	10742
	4 - I am currently responsible for taking care of someone in need and I have been responsible for taking care of someone in	18,7	5506
	98 - Don't know	2,1	632
	99 - Prefer not to answer	2,2	643

Technological variables

Energy is viewed here as a socio-technical system. Social factors and technical factors interact to shape the energy consumption of a society. Accordingly, technical predictors are also considered, which enable statements to be made about the way in which energy is consumed in the households of the people surveyed. The predictors are listed in Table 9.

The items used to measure energy consumption were taken from a questionnaire endorsed by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Bank (World Health Organization, 2019) and used to monitor SDG indicators 7.1.1 and 7.1.2. Correspondingly, the questionnaire assesses primary reliance on clean fuels and technologies, as well as access to electricity. Furthermore, it queries various facets, including the sources of household electricity consumption, household cooking patterns, household heating practices, and household lighting preferences. The selection of questionnaire items was made with the intention of ensuring their applicability to both the Global North and the Global South contexts.⁴

⁴ At the same time, there are clear differences in the comprehensibility of the items between the Global North and South. For example, the data shows misunderstandings in the

Table 9: Margin (%) and sample size (n) of the technological predictor Variables with Variable Labels and item wording.

Variable labels	Item wording	Margin %	N
QD1 - Is any food or drink cooked or prepared at the household dwelling using a cookstove, fire or other cooking device?	1 - Yes	93,2	27506
	2 - No	5,7	1691
	99 - Don't know	0,8	227
	98 - Prefer not to answer	0,3	83
QD2 - What does this household use for cooking most of the time including cooking food, making tea/coffee, boiling drinking water?	1 - Solar cooker (thermal energy, not solar panels)	0,9	259
	2 - Electric stove	38,1	11229
	3 - Piped Natural Gas Stove	16,0	4733
	4 - Biogas stove	2,0	597
	5 - Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG)/ cooking gas stove	19,7	5819
	6 - Manufactured solid fuel stove	1,4	425
	7 - Traditional solid fuel stove (non-manufactured)	3,1	903
	8 - Liquid fuel stove	1,3	389
	9 - Moveable firepan	0,9	259
	10 - Three stone stove/open fire	3,3	972
	11 - Other, specify:	4,2	1233
	97 - System (Question was not shown)	6,8	2001
	98 - Don't know	2,0	584
QD3 - What type of fuel or energy source does this household use most of the time in this cookstove or device for cooking food, making tea/coffee and boiling drinking water?	1 - Alcohol/ethanol	0,1	23
	2 - Gasoline/diesel (not in generator)	0,3	90
	3 - Kerosene/paraffin	0,2	73
	4 - Coal/lignite unprocessed	0,1	40
	5 - Coal/lignite briquettes/pellets	0,1	40
	6 - Charcoal unprocessed	1,8	521
	7 - Charcoal briquettes/pellets	0,8	227
	8 - Wood	0,7	211
	9 - Agricultural or crop residue/ grass/straw/shrubs/corn cobs	0,1	22
	10 - Animal waste/dung	0,0	5
	11 - Processed biomass pellets/briquettes	0,1	26
	12 - Woodchips	0,2	51
	13 - Garbage/plastic	0,1	17
	14 - Sawdust	0,1	18
	15 - Other	2,9	854
	97 - System (Question was not shown)	91,3	26947
	98 - Don't know	1,0	285
99 - Prefer not to answer	0,2	47	
QD4 - Does this household use any heating device or fire to keep the	1 - Yes	63,3	18693
	2 - No	34,8	10280
	98 - Don't know	1,5	435

question "Does this household use any heating device or fire to keep the dwelling/living quarters warm at any time during the year?". In countries such as Germany and Sweden, where heating is a standard feature of every home, this question was answered in the negative considerably more often than in the other countries in the North that were analysed. The response behaviour can be interpreted to mean that people in Germany and Sweden tend to use the pre-installed heating devices in their homes much more as a matter of course than people in the other countries surveyed.

dwelling/living quarters warm at any time during the year?	99 - Prefer not to answer	0,3	100	
QD5 - In the last 12 months, during how many months did you use a heating device or fire to keep the dwelling/living quarters warm?	1 month	4,3	1279	
	2 months	5,8	1715	
	3 months	8,1	2386	
	4 months	8,8	2604	
	5 months	8,1	2404	
	6 months	7,3	2166	
	7 months	3,6	1052	
	8 months	2,3	684	
	9 months	0,9	279	
	10 months	1,6	476	
	11 months	0,3	88	
	12 months	3,0	880	
		97 - System (Question was not shown)	45,7	13495
QD6 - What does this household use to heat the home when needed for the most time?	1 - Central heating	21,5	6339	
	2 - Manufactured space heater	7,3	2140	
	3 - Traditional space heater	7,8	2294	
	4 - Manufactured cookstove	2,9	866	
	5 - Traditional cookstove (non-manufactured)	2,7	808	
	6 - Mobile heating pan	1,8	527	
	7 - Open fire/Three-stone stove	4,9	1458	
	8 - Heat pump	6,2	1841	
	9 - Other, specify:	6,0	1784	
		97 - System (Question was not shown)	37,6	11107
		98 - Don't know	0,9	258
		99 - Prefer not to answer	0,3	86
	QD7 - What type of fuel or energy source does this household use most of the time for heating in this heater, cookstove or device?	1 - Electricity (including solar panels)	18,0	5312
2 - Piped Natural Gas		12,5	3683	
3 - LPG/cooking gas		6,6	1939	
4 - Biogas		1,0	309	
5 - Alcohol/ethanol		0,3	87	
6 - Gasoline/diesel (not in generator)		1,0	298	
7 - Kerosene/paraffin		0,9	259	
8 - Coal/lignite unprocessed		0,8	233	
9 - Coal/lignite briquettes/pellets		0,8	238	
10 - Charcoal unprocessed		1,6	479	
11 - Charcoal briquettes/pellets		1,9	568	
12 - Wood		7,5	2207	
13 - Agricultural or crop residue/grass/straw/shrubs/corn cobs		0,3	87	
14 - Animal waste/dung		0,1	44	
15 - Processed biomass pellets/briquettes		1,3	371	
16 - Woodchips		0,8	229	
17 - Garbage/plastic		0,2	56	
18 - Sawdust		0,2	65	
19 - Other		2,6	764	
		97 - System (Question was not shown)	37,7	11107
	98 - Don't know	3,7	1082	
	99 - Prefer not to answer	0,3	92	
QD8 - Does this household use anything for lighting?	1 - Yes	93,6	27605	
	2 - No	4,6	1368	
	98 - Don't know	1,5	439	
	99 - Prefer not to answer	0,3	95	
QD9 - What does this household use most of the time as energy for lighting, or as a light source?	1 - Electricity (including solar panels)	74,2	21880	
	2 - Solar powered lantern or flashlight	2,9	845	
	3 - Rechargeable flashlight, mobile, torch or lantern	3,5	1028	

	4 - Battery powered flashlight, torch or lantern	1,9	563
	6 - Biogas lamp	0,5	142
	7 - LPG lamp	1,3	370
	8 - Gasoline lamp	0,5	145
	9 - Kerosene or paraffin lamp	0,8	235
	10 - Oil lamp	0,5	145
	11 - Candle	2,1	622
	12 - Open fire	0,9	258
	13 - Other	2,6	777
	97 – System (Question was not shown)	6,4	1902
	98 - Don't know	1,6	473
	99 - Prefer not to answer	0,4	122
QD10 - What source of electricity is used most of the time in this household?	1 - No electricity in household	0,8	241
	2 - National grid connection	63,4	18711
	3 - Local mini grid	3,3	974
	4 - Solar home system	7,8	2311
	5 - Solar lantern	2,0	577
	6 - Electric generator	7,5	2208
	7 - Rechargeable battery	2,2	657
	8 - Dry cell battery/ torch	1,1	312
	9 - Other, specify:	1,9	557
	97 – System (Question was not shown)	6,4	1902
	98 - Don't know	3,1	907
	99 - Prefer not to answer	0,5	149

Control variables

Presumably central predictors of experiences of marginalisation in the context of energy consumption and energy citizenship are income and level of education. These variables were also surveyed as they are considerable markers of an individual's social class, but are not assigned to the intersectional variables here. In the sense of the capital theory described at the beginning, these are resources that are acquired over the course of a lifetime. The chances of acquiring a sufficient level of income and education are in turn often influenced by the intersectional variables—in particular the primary identity characteristics. In this sense, income and education are integrated as control variables into as shown in Table 10. This means that income and education were part of the random forest analyses and education was part of the decision tree analyses.

Item wording was provided by the service provider commissioned to conduct the survey. Income was measured both in numerical categories and in terms of self-assessment of how sufficient the income is. Only this self-assessment is considered here, as the corresponding answers are comparable across national borders without any further adjustments. The level of education was determined based on the highest educational qualification achieved and classified as low, medium or high according to the respective national education system.

Unlike a person's current income and level of education, the income and level of education of a person's parents are primary identity characteristics. Class origin in this sense was not recorded in the study.

Table 10: Margin (%) and sample size (n) of the intersectional predictor Variables with Variable Labels and item wording.

<i>Variable labels</i>	<i>item wording</i>	<i>Margin %</i>	<i>N</i>
Education level	1 - Low education	14,7	4329
	2 - Medium education	42,1	12422
	3 - High education	43,2	12759
Which of the following descriptions comes closest to how you feel about your household's income nowadays?	1 - Living comfortably on present income	20,8	6124
	2 - Coping on present income	43,2	12749
	3 - Finding it difficult on present income	23,7	7004
	4 - Finding it very difficult on present income	10,0	2938
	98 - Don't know	0,7	196
	99 - Prefer not to answer	1,7	497

Analytical procedure: intersectional exploration through machine learning techniques

With this study, our aim is to systematically examine the interplay of intersecting influences on experiences of energy marginalisation, energy use, and environmental behaviour across ten countries in a representative manner. It is important to note that our quantitative approach to intersectional patterns in energy consumption and citizenship is an endeavour remarkably rare in research. Additionally, the translation of intersectionality from theory to quantitative methodology is frequently prone to misinterpretation (Bauer et al. 2021). Undoubtedly, an understanding is necessary of the features that characterize quantitative intersectionality analysis. (Bauer et al. 2021).

Scott and Siltanen (2017) meticulously outline three crucial elements that form the foundation of an intersectional approach to quantitative research, drawing insights from the rich tapestry of feminist literature. At the forefront, they emphasize the imperative of conducting analyses with a nuanced appreciation for context sensitivity. This involves not only integrating relevant variables into regression equations but also navigating the complexities of different contextual conditions. By incorporating context into the analytical framework, researchers can gain a deeper understanding under which conditions particular experiences of marginalisation occur. Second, a heuristic approach should be used to identify relevant categories of inequality. In practice, this means that a study should be partly exploratory and should not prematurely narrow the view of relevant dimensions of inequality according to fixed a priori assumptions. Third, the analysis should capture the complexity of intersectionality and social reality. This means that intersectionality should not be viewed in an

exclusively additive way⁵, but that the combination of different identity characteristics can be reflected in diverse and context-dependent interaction effects.

In the view of Scott and Siltanen (2017), multilevel regression models best fulfil the conditions of the intersectional paradigm they describe in quantitative social research. More recent research has significantly expanded the methodological canon of the intersectional quantitative paradigm. In a simulation study, Mahendran et al. (2022) compared the advantages and disadvantages of classic regressions, the multi-level analysis of individual heterogeneity and discriminatory accuracy (MAIHDA), as well as decision trees and random forest analyses. As a result, they recommend using decision trees and random forests in highly explorative contexts in which there are no theoretical assumptions about the interactions between many variables. In this way, important variables and intersections between their categories can be identified, which can then be analysed in greater depth in targeted regression analyses.

In line with the exploratory nature of the present study, decision trees (SPSS CHAID algorithm) were used to identify presumably interesting interactions between intersectional and technical variables in the context of various phenomena of energy marginalisation for further theoretical studies. Additionally, random forests (R random-Forest package) were applied to identify variables with a high predictive power.

CHAID (Chi-Squared Automatic Interaction Detector) decision trees work by splitting the data into groups based on statistically significant differences, forming a tree-like structure that highlights key patterns and interactions. In contrast, random forests consist of multiple decision trees that work together to improve prediction accuracy by averaging their results, making the model more robust and reliable.

The data patterns determined using decision trees and random forest analyses cannot stand alone. An interpretative classification was drawn up for all the phenomena of energy marginalisation investigated. Such a classification also appears important due to so-called methodological artefacts in the decision trees and random forests:

- Decision trees contain white noise, defined here as random signals unrelated to observed phenomena. They group features by similar response averages, merging large groups (e.g., 150 solar home system users) with small ones with randomly similar mean values (e.g., 5 dry cell battery users). For a coherent interpretation of the decision tree, such white noise needs to be identified and neglected for the interpretation of the data pattern.

⁵ To put it somewhat pointedly, this would be, for example, the assumption that a black woman who belongs to a minority is generally more discriminated against than a black man who belongs to a minority or a white woman who belongs to the majority.

- Random forest models tend to assign higher variable importance to continuous variables and categorical variables with many categories.
- Since the focus of gEneSys is on the exploration of gender effects, the integration of the variable gender was enforced in all decision trees by a corresponding code command. This means that all decision trees differentiate according to gender, even if the algorithm of the decision tree would otherwise not have taken gender into account due to insufficient predictive power.

The data patterns determined therefore require an interpretive categorisation to condense the computational data patterns into meaningful data patterns that are only then useful for future research. The corresponding interpretations were based on the systematic literature review conducted in gEneSys (Cellini et al., 2025), on reflection discussions within the research team and on five reflection discussions with thematic experts (see box). The calculated data patterns were presented to the experts in one-hour virtual workshops on a digital whiteboard. The experts' thoughts were recorded on the whiteboard using sticky notes.

Experts who participated in the Data Interpretation Sessions

Dr. Arn Sauer, Director, Federal Foundation for Gender Equality, Germany

Prof. Saska Petrova, Professor of Human Geography, University of Manchester, UK

Dr. Rosie Day, Associate Professor in Environment and Society, University of Birmingham, UK

Dr. Panu Pihkala, Adjunct Professor of Environmental Theology, University of Helsinki, Finland

Prof. Jens Lowitzsch, Professor, European University Viadrina, Germany

At the end of the report, an unusual exercise has been undertaken: behind the abstracted data lie the lived realities and experiences of marginalisation of real people. To retranslate the conducted analyses and the identified intersectional data patterns back into practice, concrete personas were created based on these findings. We argue that this transfer of our research results is what truly enables a user- and citizen-oriented policy design.

To generate the personas exemplified at the end of the report, the report was uploaded into ChatGPT 4o, and the following prompt was used:

"Please carefully analyse the attached report. Based on the identified intersectional data patterns, create four exemplary personas. These personas should differ in their combinations of financial, social, cultural, and infrastructural capital. Due to their differing capital resources, they experience varying forms of energy marginalisation. Generate brief descriptions and create a respectful visual representation for each persona."

The generated texts and images were incorporated into this report with minimal revisions. These personas serve as a basis for discussing concrete policies for an inclusive energy transition in the closing chapter of this report.

RESULTS: INTERSECTIONAL PATTERNS OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND ENERGY CITIZENSHIP IN GLOBAL NORTH AND SOUTH

The five outcomes examined are intended to investigate experiences of marginalisation in relation to energy consumption and energy citizenship in greater depth. This raises the question of the content validity of the variables and indices used for this purpose. This means that insofar as the indices analysed here actually measure aspects of experiences of marginalisation, they would be expected to correlate with a feeling of personal disadvantage.

The PRDI was used to measure the so-called feeling of deprivation (Callan et al., 2011). The PRDI measures the extent to which individuals feel disadvantaged compared to an abstract reference group ("people like me"). Figure 1 reports the results of a correlation analysis between PRDI and the four outcome indices. This shows medium to large effects for almost all indices (following the effect size benchmarks of Funder and Ozer (2019)). The correlation between the Energy Poverty Index and PRDI is particularly pronounced. The correlation between the Energy Poverty Index and ESCI and the PRDI is negative. This means that the less a person sees their energy consumption as affordable or the less they see themselves as capable of organising their energy consumption sustainably, the higher their feeling of deprivation tends to be. The correlation between the Eco Anxiety Index and PRDI is positive. This means that the more feelings of stress a person reports in connection with climate change, the more pronounced their sense of deprivation tends to be.

Although statistically significant, the correlation between EPSEI and PRDI is practically insignificant due to its low effect size. The very weak correlation indicates that a feeling of a lack of political efficacy in relation to energy policy does not tend to go hand in hand with a general feeling of being disadvantaged.

Figure 1: Correlations (Pearson) of the outcome indices with the Personal Relative Deprivation Index. All correlations have p-values < 0.001. Note that indices have different scale directions: high values on Energy Poverty Index mean low energy poverty, high values on EPSEI mean high energy political self-efficacy, high values on ESCI mean high energy sustainability capability, high values on Eco Anxiety Index mean high eco anxiety.

The following subsections follow a clear sequence presenting a systematic analysis of the respective outcomes. First, the outcome itself is defined and discussed regarding aspects influencing response behaviour. This is followed by a country-specific analysis of gender gaps within the outcome to identify and highlight key differences. Next, the main predictors of the outcome in the Global North and Global South are assessed using Random Forest analyses.

In the subsequent step, groups with particularly strong deviations from the overall mean are identified through decision tree models and analysed in detail. To provide a systematic overview of these extreme groups, we present and discuss the groups with the highest and lowest mean values for each outcome. These groups are categorized by binary gender (men and women) and region (Global North and Global South) and are derived from decision trees that use either exclusively intersectional predictors or a combination of intersectional and technical predictors—resulting in a total of 16 groups per outcome. If two groups had similarly high mean values (difference of less than 0.1), the group with the larger sample size was selected. The selection grid described above is summarised in figure 2. Finally, all findings of a subsection are interpreted through the lens of capital theory to explore structural influences and mechanisms of marginalisation.

The exact data of all charts presented in this report are listed in the annex to the report.

Figure 2: Selection scheme for the 16 group differences reported and interpreted per outcome.

A recommendation for reading this report

As each of the five outcomes examined in this report has been analysed using the four methodological and interpretative approaches (Gender Gaps by Country, Random Forests, Extreme Group Comparison, and Capital Theory Interpretation), some redundancy in the presentation was unavoidable. Readers seeking a quick overview of the findings are recommended to go directly to Chapter 5: Summary of Results, while those with a deeper interest can refer to the specific analyses of the outcome they are most interested in.

Energy poverty

The Energy Poverty Index is designed to measure robust experiences of energy poverty. It is based on a more holistic understanding of energy poverty, as proposed by Day et al. (2016), which extends beyond conventional definitions that primarily focus on whether a household has sufficient financial resources in relation to its energy demand. Day et al. (ibidem) define energy poverty as:

"[...] an inability to realise essential capabilities as a direct or indirect result of insufficient access to affordable, reliable, and safe energy services, and taking into account available reasonable alternative means of realising these capabilities. [...]"

This definition acknowledges that energy needs and expectations vary across households and that their significance differs depending on the specific household. Energy poverty, therefore, exists when a person is unable to fulfil the basic human purposes for which they consume energy in their household.

This concept, based on the capability approach developed by Amartya Sen and Martha Nussbaum (Nussbaum, 2000), was extensively incorporated into the questionnaire design used in this study (see also the section on the ESCI). The Energy Poverty Index synthesizes what we consider the most essential variables. It measures an individual's subjective perception of whether the energy required to sustain their household is affordable, accessible, reliable, and safe (i.e., not harmful to health). Consequently, a person's response behaviour is likely influenced by:

- 1) the household's total energy needs,
- 2) the household's financial resources,
- 3) whether the respondent directly bears the cost of their household's energy consumption or merely provides an indirect assessment as a simple household member, and
- 4) the infrastructural conditions in which they live (i.e., what energy sources are available, how scarce they are, and their reliability) (Bouzarovski & Petrova, 2015).

In this context, the Energy Poverty Index captures experiences of marginalization when individuals perceive that their desired household energy consumption and its energy-related purposes are restricted by insufficient financial or infrastructural resources.

From the perspective of the capital theory applied in this report, it is expected that individuals with lower levels of economic capital will score lower on the Energy Poverty Index. Energy is a consumer good that incurs costs. While individuals with greater economic capital tend to have higher absolute energy expenditures, these higher costs are primarily driven by discretionary consumption (i.e., voluntary spending on non-essential goods and services) and are therefore perceived as less restrictive (Li et al., 2022). We assume that cultural or social capital is only relevant to the Energy Poverty Index insofar as it indirectly influences an individual's level of economic capital.

Country wise Gender Gaps in the Energy Poverty Index

In Figure 3, the mean value of the Energy Poverty Index for men and women across the studied countries is presented. The index tends to be considerably higher in the Global North compared to the Global South, suggesting that energy poverty is a much more widespread phenomenon in the African countries examined than in the European ones.

Among the countries of the Global South, Uganda stands out with the lowest mean value for both men and women. Here, energy poverty appears to be the most

prevalent of all the countries studied. This is plausible given that Uganda has by far the lowest per capita income among all nations (see section on country selection).

Even within the Global North, there is considerable variation. Subjectively perceived energy poverty is less common in Sweden and Germany—the two countries with the highest per capita income in the sample—compared to France, Italy, Poland, and Portugal.

Gender differences in subjectively perceived energy poverty are generally small across all countries studied (threshold for Hedges' $g = 0.1$). However, significant and statistically meaningful differences ($p < .001$) are observed in France ($g = .15$), Portugal ($g = .12$), Sweden ($g = .12$), and Kenya ($g = -.13$). Notably, in Kenya men tend to report lower levels of perceived energy poverty, which contradicts current research findings indicating that women are generally more affected by energy poverty (Blouzarovski & Petrova, 2015; Clancy et al., 2017; Petrova & Simcock, 2019).

The results show higher energy poverty in the Global South, with notable regional variations. Wealthier countries report lower levels, while gender differences remain small but significant, with men in some cases perceiving less energy poverty than expected.

Figure 3: Country wise Gender Gap in the Energy Poverty Index. Weighted descriptive means of ANOVA. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

The ten most important predictors of the Energy Poverty Index

The Energy Poverty Index highlights regional differences in energy vulnerability, with energy access and affordability playing key roles. While both the Global North and South share similar predictors, their influence differs significantly as it is displayed in Figure 4.

Energy source availability for heating, cooking, and electricity is the strongest determinant in both regions. In the Global South, main electricity source (68.7), main fuel for heating (66.2), and main fuel for cooking (61.5) dominate, indicating that energy poverty is driven by infrastructural deficits. In the Global North, these same factors have much lower importance (electricity: 5.2, heating: 12.1, cooking: 10.1).

Urbanity is a strong predictor in the Global South (56.5 vs. 10.0 in the North), showing that rural populations face higher risks due to weak infrastructure. Household income perception is more influential in the Global South (52.4 vs. 9.2), reflecting direct financial barriers to energy access (see annex table 4.2.2). Age has a greater impact in the Global South (35.4 vs. 8.8), likely due to financial dependence and limited household control.

However, a Spearman correlation for the predictor rankings in Global North and South of 0.84 ($p < .001$) shows high regional consistency in predictor ranking. This consistency suggests energy poverty is a universal structural issue.

Finally, also caregiving responsibilities and household structure have a greater impact on energy poverty in the Global South, with caregiving (28.2 vs. 4.9) and living situation (32.1 vs. 5.6) emerging as key predictors. Gender identity is more relevant in the Global South (6.1 vs. 1.1), reflecting disparities in energy access.

The comparison between the Global North and South shows that the predictive quality of the predictor models used is significantly better for the Global South. In other words, it is much more difficult to reliably predict whether an individual will suffer from energy poverty in the Global North. Individual-situational (presumably also psychosocial) factors appear to play a relatively more important role in the Global North when it comes to experiencing energy poverty.

Figure 4: Top 10 variables for predicting the Energy Poverty IndexI in Global North and Global South plus Gender identity. Increase in Node Purity of ESCI Random Forest Analysis. Cutoff after ten predictors dependent from Global North.

Extreme group analysis for the Energy Poverty Index

The analysis of extreme deviations in the Energy Poverty Index based on a set of decision tree analyses is shown in Figure 5. In the Global South, the groups experiencing the highest levels of energy poverty tend to live in rural or semi-urban areas and rely on traditional cooking and heating methods, such as three-stone stoves, open fires, or unprocessed coal. However, in urban areas of the Global South, the picture shifts.

Individuals who have access to modern heating and cooking technologies, such as central heating or electric stoves, report considerably lower energy poverty levels. This highlights how infrastructure plays a crucial role in reducing energy-related marginalisation. Unlike in the Global North, there is no clear pattern of gender differences in the way energy poverty relates to specific energy sources or appliances.

In the Global North, energy poverty is generally lower, but certain groups still experience heightened vulnerability. Individuals using non-standard electricity sources, such as generators or rechargeable batteries, as well as those relying on solid or liquid fuel stoves, tend to report higher levels of energy poverty. A notable pattern emerges in how energy poverty is linked to different energy sources for men and women. Among men in the Global North, the type of electricity source appears to be a key predictor, with those dependent on non-grid electricity experiencing higher energy poverty. For women, the type of cooking appliance is more closely linked to energy poverty, with higher levels found among those using traditional or solid fuel stoves. This suggests that, in the Global North, energy poverty manifests differently depending on gender, with men's experiences shaped more by their electricity access and women's by their cooking technology.

Across both regions, some clear trends emerge. Energy access and the type of fuel used are the strongest predictors of energy poverty, with traditional cooking and heating methods being closely linked to higher levels of deprivation. Urban residence generally reduces energy poverty, especially when it is combined with modern energy infrastructure. In the Global South, gender differences in energy poverty are less pronounced, whereas in the Global North, men's and women's energy poverty experiences appear to be linked to different aspects of household energy use.

Overall, these findings underline the fact that energy poverty is primarily driven by access to infrastructure and energy sources, with factors such as geography, socio-economic status, and energy-use patterns shaping individual experiences of energy poverty.

Figure 5: Selection of groups formed by the socio-technical and intersectional decision trees for the Global North and South for the Energy Poverty Index with clear positive and negative deviations from the overall average Energy Poverty Index. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

Extreme Cases of Energy Poverty Index

The results from the perspective of capital theory

The findings are in line with the initially stated assumption that economic capital is the strongest determinant of energy poverty. In the Global South, energy poverty is

shaped by infrastructure and urbanity, while in the Global North, elusive individual-situational aspects play a greater role. Cultural and social capital have a limited direct effect in both regions, as financial and structural constraints often override energy choices.

Analysing the extreme groups shows that economic capital behaves differently in the Global North and South. Rural populations in the Global South using traditional fuels for cooking and heating face the highest energy poverty, whereas in the Global North, non-grid electricity and solid fuel heating are key indicators.

Gender differences are more evident in the North, where men's energy poverty is linked to electricity access, while women's is tied to cooking appliances. Energy literacy as a form of cultural capital and social capital—including household decision-making—might shape these patterns in Global North.

Energy political self-efficacy

In psychological terms, political efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their political competence and influence (Beierlein et al., 2012; Campbell et al., 1954). This belief is differentiated into an internal and external dimension (Beierlein et al., 2012). The internal dimension assesses an individual's sense of political competence—that is, the feeling of having sufficient political knowledge to form an opinion and engage in political discussions. The external dimension, on the other hand, measures trust in politicians—the perception that politicians are genuinely interested in the concerns of citizens.

As part of the gEneSys citizen survey, the English version of the Political Efficacy Short Scale was administered (Beierlein, 2014). The four items of this scale were supplemented with additional, nearly identical items specifically related to energy policy, forming the Energy Political Self-Efficacy Index (EPSEI). This means that respondents first provided a general assessment of their political efficacy and then immediately afterwards evaluated their energy political efficacy. Consequently, participants consciously contrasted their perceptions of general and energy-specific political efficacy.

The EPSEI introduced here measures individuals' perceived efficacy in energy policy and, in doing so, also reflects experiences of (energy-)political marginalisation. Marginalised groups often exhibit lower political self-efficacy, as social inequality and educational disadvantages limit their access to political knowledge (Delli Carpini & Keeter, 1996; Verba, Schlozman & Brady, 1995). At the same time, they tend to perceive state institutions as distant, which diminishes their trust in institutional responsiveness (Schlozman, Verba & Brady, 2012; Solt, 2008). While low internal efficacy discourages political engagement due to self-doubt, low external efficacy often leads to disengagement out of frustration—perpetuating a cycle of political exclusion.

From the perspective of capital theory, it can be assumed that energy political self-efficacy is influenced by both social and cultural capital. In the internal dimension of political self-efficacy, respondents assess their political knowledge and substantive competence—both of which are largely shaped by their level of education (Beierlein, 2012). The external dimension, on the other hand, reflects an individual's trust in institutions and politicians. This trust tends to be stronger among socially integrated individuals (Putnam, 2000).

Country wise Gender Gaps in the EPSEI

In Figure 6, the mean values of the EPSEI for men and women across the analysed countries are displayed. A clear regional trend emerges, with gender-specific EPSEI values being consistently higher in the Global South than in the Global North. This indicates that individuals in Kenya, Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa perceive themselves as having greater political agency in energy-related matters compared to those in European countries.

Among the countries of the Global South, Nigeria exhibits slightly higher values. In the Global North, EPSEI levels are also largely similar across countries, with German men reporting the highest mean value.

Across all examined countries, men report higher levels of EPSEI than women, with the gender gap being statistically significant ($p < .001$). The largest gender differences are observed in France ($g = .46$), Germany ($g = .50$), Sweden ($g = .52$), Poland ($g = .36$), and Italy ($g = .31$), whereas gender differences in African countries tend to be smaller (e.g., Nigeria with $g = .24$). These findings align with research indicating that men often perceive themselves as more politically effective than women, despite evidence that women actively engage in energy policy activism (McCright & Dunlap, 2011).

Overall, these results suggest that energy political self-efficacy is shaped by both regional and gendered dynamics. While individuals in the Global South generally report greater confidence in influencing energy policy, significant gender disparities persist across all examined nations.

Figure 6: Country wise Gender Gap in the EPSEI. Weighted descriptive means of ANOVA. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

The ten most important predictors of the EPSEI

Access to energy sources for heating, cooking, and lighting is a key predictor in both regions but less pronounced than in the Energy Poverty Index (see Figure 7). In the Global South, main fuel for heating (24.8), main fuel for cooking (19.3), and main lighting source (16.5) indicate that stable access to modern energy sources correlates with higher political self-efficacy. In the Global North, these factors have lower importance (heating: 12.1, cooking: 10.1, lighting: 7.7), suggesting that political self-efficacy is shaped more by individual and social factors.

Urbanity is a stronger predictor in the Global South (17.9 vs. 6.8), suggesting greater perceived opportunities for political engagement in cities. Household income perception has a greater impact in the Global South (8.3 vs. 3.3), though it is much less influential than in the Energy Poverty Index, indicating that financial stability is secondary to energy political self-efficacy. Age is more relevant in the Global South (10.2 vs. 4.6), indicating that older individuals feel more confident engaging in energy policy.

A Spearman correlation between the Global North and South predictors of 0.94 ($p < .001$) suggests strong regional consistency in predictor importance, indicating that the general order of importance of the EPSEI predictors is very similar for Global North and South.

Caregiving responsibilities are associated with higher political self-efficacy in both regions, with a slightly stronger effect in the Global South (8.3 vs. 5.5). A similar pattern

exists for living situation (13.0 vs. 3.6), suggesting that individuals in larger households report higher confidence in political engagement. Gender identity has a greater impact in the Global South (2.2 vs. 0.5).

Compared to other indices, EPSEI focuses on perceived agency rather than material conditions. While the Energy Poverty Index is shaped by access and affordability, and the Renewable Energy (Co-)Ownership Index by financial resources, EPSEI depends more on individual and social factors. Its high Spearman correlation suggests political self-efficacy is even more universally structured than energy poverty, allowing more standardised policies and mutual learning between Global North and South.

Figure 7: Top 10 variables for predicting the Energy Poverty Index¹ in Global North and Global South plus Gender identity. Increase in Node Purity's of EPSEI Random Forest Analysis. Cutoff after ten predictors dependent from Global North.

Extreme group analysis for the EPSEI

The decision tree-based analysis of extreme deviations in the EPSEI is displayed in Figure 8. In the Global South, individuals without caregiving responsibilities and without

heating devices in their household tend to report the lowest political self-efficacy. This indicates that access to heating infrastructure and social integration may contribute to self-perceived political agency. By contrast, higher EPSEI scores are found among individuals in very urban areas and those with access to modern heating technologies, such as central heating or heat pumps. This suggests that urbanisation and infrastructure access enhance perceptions of political influence, likely due to greater exposure to energy governance and participation opportunities. Caregiving also appears to increase political self-efficacy, particularly for men in Nigeria and women in urban areas, possibly reflecting stronger social ties and a sense of responsibility in decision-making.

In the Global North, the lowest EPSEI scores are associated with low education levels. Women with low education and without minority group identification report particularly low confidence, as do those who have not named or could not name their source of electricity. Conversely, men with higher education, particularly in Germany, report higher EPSEI scores, as do those using unconventional cooking methods such as solar cookers, firepans, or solid fuel stoves. The latter pattern may suggest a link between political engagement and alternative energy choices, possibly reflecting higher awareness of energy policy debates among users of non-mainstream energy sources.

Across both regions, some clear patterns emerge. Caregiving responsibilities, and education consistently correlate with higher political self-efficacy, whereas low education and lack of caregiving duties are associated with lower confidence in energy policy engagement. Gender differences are more pronounced in the Global North, where women with low education report particularly low EPSEI scores.

Overall, these findings suggest that access to education and caregiving responsibilities play a central role in shaping political engagement in energy policy. In the Global South, urbanisation and caregiving increase self-efficacy, whereas in the Global North, first and foremost education appears to be decisive.

Figure 8: Selection of groups formed by the socio-technical and intersectional decision trees for the Global North and South for the EPSEI with clear positive and negative deviations from the overall average EPSEI. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

The results from the perspective of capital theory

The findings imply that energy political self-efficacy is primarily shaped by social and cultural capital, aligning with the initial assumption that political knowledge, social integration, and institutional engagement play key roles.

In the Global South, caregiving responsibilities and urban residence are linked to higher EPSEI, suggesting that social capital—represented through caregiving—enhances political agency. Conversely, individuals without caregiving duties and without access to heating infrastructure report the lowest EPSEI, indicating that limited social integration and infrastructural barriers reduce political confidence.

In the Global North, education and engagement with institutional energy systems appear more decisive. Individuals with low education report the lowest EPSEI scores, reinforcing that cultural capital—knowledge of energy infrastructure and governance—shapes political self-efficacy. Conversely, men in Germany and individuals using alternative cooking technologies, such as solar cookers and firepans, as well as individuals relying on non-grid electricity sources, such as solar home systems or generators, exhibit higher EPSEI. This suggests that engagement with decentralised energy solutions fosters political confidence.

Overall, the findings support that EPSEI is shaped more by social and cultural capital than by economic resources. In the Global South, caregiving responsibilities and urban integration enhance political agency, while in the Global North, education, energy knowledge, and institutional engagement play a stronger role. Policies aiming to increase political participation in energy governance should focus on expanding social networks and energy awareness to strengthen self-efficacy across regions.

(Co-)ownership of renewable energy production installation or storage facility

(Co-)Ownership of Renewable Energy (RE) Production Installation or Storage Facility is a single item which measured whether an individual identifies as an owner or co-owner of a renewable energy production installation or storage facility. This variable captures the extent to which individuals are directly involved in decentralized energy production and storage, reflecting their level of engagement in the energy transition.

Ownership of RE infrastructure is a key aspect of energy citizenship, as it enables individuals to participate actively in energy markets, reduce dependency on external providers, and potentially benefit financially from self-generated or stored energy. However, participation in renewable energy ownership is likely influenced by multiple factors, including:

- 1) financial resources, as investments in renewable energy systems or storage facilities require significant upfront capital.
- 2) access to infrastructure, since owning renewable energy installations depends on property rights and technical feasibility (e.g., rooftop suitability for solar panels).

- 3) regulatory frameworks and incentives, which can either encourage or hinder individual investments in renewable energy production.
- 4) knowledge and awareness, as ownership decisions may depend on an individual's understanding of energy technologies, financial viability, and available subsidies.

The lack of ownership of RE production or storage facilities can serve as an indicator of marginalization as individuals without access to renewable energy ownership—whether due to financial constraints, housing situations (e.g., renters vs. homeowners), or lack of institutional support—experience structural disadvantages in benefiting from decentralized energy systems (Simcock, Willis, & Capener, 2016). The dominance of large-scale corporate energy providers in many regions limits opportunities for marginalized groups to participate in local energy governance and decision-making, reinforcing energy-related inequalities (Bouzarovski & Simcock, 2017).

Furthermore, energy ownership is a key determinant of energy autonomy (Radtke, 2014). Households without renewable energy systems remain dependent on market-driven energy pricing, making them more vulnerable to energy poverty and price fluctuations (Middlemiss & Gillard, 2015). This disproportionately affects low-income populations, who already allocate a higher share of their income to energy costs (Bouzarovski, 2014). Thus, the ability to generate and store renewable energy is not only an environmental and economic advantage but also a form of social and political empowerment, shaping who has control over energy access and decision-making (Van Veelen, 2018).

From a capital theory perspective, individuals with higher economic capital are more likely to own RE systems due to their ability to invest long-term. Cultural capital can also play a role, fostering interest in energy technologies (Jenkins et al., 2016). Additionally, social capital—through peer networks and cooperatives—facilitates shared ownership and broader participation (Walker et al., 2007).

Country wise Gender Gaps in the (Co-)ownership of RE

The proportion of male and female respondents in the examined countries who self-reported as (co-)owners of a renewable energy production or storage facility is presented in Figure 9. No clear pattern emerges indicating that RE (co-)ownership is more prevalent in either the Global North or the Global South. Instead, this outcome appears to be strongly influenced by country-specific factors, such as the extent of national grid development.

At the national level, the highest share of RE (co-)owners is found among German men. In the Global South, Nigerian men exhibit similarly high levels of RE (co-)ownership. In contrast, French and Swedish women in the Global North are the least likely

to be RE (co-)owners. A similarly low share is observed among Ugandan women, who overall report the lowest levels of RE (co-)ownership across all examined countries.

In the Global North, several countries exhibit weak but statistically significant gender gaps ($p < .001$). Specifically, men in Sweden ($g = .23$), Italy ($g = .15$), and Germany ($g = .14$) are more likely to be RE (co-)owners than women in these countries. No statistically significant gender gaps are observed in the Global South.

Overall, the results suggest that RE (co-)ownership is shaped by both national and gendered dynamics. While access to and engagement with renewable energy technologies in the Global North appears to be influenced by gender disparities, the absence of statistically significant gender gaps in the Global South may indicate a different structuring of energy-related opportunities and barriers in these regions.

Figure 9: Country wise Gender Gap in the (Co-)ownership of RE. Weighted descriptive means of ANOVA. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

The ten most important predictors of (Co-)ownership of RE

The analysis of (co-)ownership of RE highlights regional differences in individuals' likelihood of owning or co-owning a RE production or storage facility (Figure 10). While infrastructural and financial factors influence ownership in both the Global North and South, again, their significance varies, with stronger economic constraints in the South and a more diversified set of influences in the North.

Household energy sources play a key role in both regions, but the specific patterns differ. In the Global South, main fuel for heating (14.8), main fuel for cooking (9.6), and main heating method (10.0) are relatively strong predictors, suggesting that reliance on traditional energy sources increases the likelihood of seeking alternative,

renewable options. In the Global North, main electricity source (12.2) and main lighting source (9.3) are the strongest predictors, indicating that access to certain grid infrastructures or off-grid systems influences ownership opportunities.

Urbanity plays a much stronger role in the Global South (8.6 vs. 2.4), suggesting that RE ownership is more viable in urban settings, possibly due to policy incentives or market availability. Household income perception is a stronger predictor in the Global South (14.8 vs. 1.1), reinforcing the idea that financial barriers significantly shape ownership opportunities in developing regions. Age has a moderate impact, with a stronger effect in the Global South (6.8 vs. 2.8), suggesting that renewable energy ownership increases with financial and social stability.

A Spearman correlation between the Global North and South predictors of 0.76 ($p = 0.001$) suggests lower regional consistency compared to other outcome indices. This reflects that while energy poverty and sustainability capabilities follow clear structural patterns, renewable energy ownership is shaped more by policy environments and investment opportunities, which vary widely between regions.

Social factors play a moderate role, with caregiving responsibilities (5.0 vs. 1.9) and living situation (5.0 vs. 1.5) having a stronger effect in the Global South. Here, larger households and caregiving responsibilities may indicate shared financial resources or collective investment in energy solutions. Gender identity is a minor predictor in both regions (0.9 vs. 0.4), with a slightly greater effect in the Global South.

Compared to the other outcomes analysed, it is noteworthy that in the Global South the variable importance values of the technical variables of household energy consumption are much lower. This makes RE (co-)ownership the most difficult of all outcomes to predict using the predictor models employed here. Individual situational aspects appear to be particularly decisive for this outcome.

Compared to other indices, (Co-)Ownership of RE is unique in being shaped by both infrastructural access and financial capacity. While the Energy Poverty Index reflects deprivation and the Energy Political Self-Efficacy Index captures agency, this index is more directly tied to investment feasibility. Its lower Spearman correlation suggests that ownership is less structurally, highlighting the need for targeted financial mechanisms to facilitate renewable energy adoption.

Figure 10: Top 10 variables for predicting the (Co-)ownership of RE in Global North and Global South plus Gender identity. Increase in Node Purity's of (Co-)ownership of RE. Random Forest Analysis. Cutoff after ten predictors dependent from Global North.

Extreme group analysis for the (Co-)ownership of RE

The analysis of extreme deviations in (Co-)Ownership of RE is displayed in Figure 11. Ownership appears to be shaped by financial resources, infrastructure access, and socio-economic conditions, with considerable differences between the Global North and Global South as well as between men and women.

In the Global South, ownership of RE is lowest among women in Uganda and those without access to modern heating technologies, suggesting that limited infrastructure and financial constraints strongly impact ownership opportunities. Women who rely on national grid or mini-grid electricity report very low rates of ownership, reinforcing the idea that reliance on centralised energy systems may reduce incentives or opportunities for individual renewable investments. By contrast, the highest ownership rates in the Global South are found among men in Nigeria who report mental health conditions and individuals with access to central heating or heat pumps. This suggests that access to modern heating infrastructure and possibly higher socio-economic stability facilitate renewable energy investments.

In the Global North, ownership patterns differ, with women in Sweden and Poland showing the lowest levels of participation. The highest ownership rates in the North are found among women over 38 using solar home systems and men in Germany living in multi-person households. This suggests that in the Global North, household structure and alternative energy sources play a stronger role in renewable energy adoption. Notably, men who own unconventional cooking devices such as solar cookers, firepans, or open fires also report high ownership rates, possibly reflecting a connection between off-grid energy practices and engagement with decentralised energy solutions.

Across both regions, some clear trends emerge. Infrastructure access and financial resources are the strongest predictors RE ownership, with ownership being significantly lower among those relying on traditional heating and cooking methods. In the Global North, ownership is more diversified, with a mix of technological, financial, and social factors shaping participation, while in the Global South, financial capacity and infrastructure access play a more dominant role.

In the Global South as well as in the Global North, gender differences in ownership appear to be less structured, with socio-economic factors and infrastructure access playing a stronger role than gender identity itself.

To summarise, the data gives the impression that RE (co-)ownership in the Global South is strongly dependent on the socio-economic status of a household, in particular the highest level of education of the household members. In the Global North, somewhat similarly, but differently, more consolidated households seem to tend towards RE (co-)ownership. In other words, households whose inhabitants are in more settled phases of life and who have found "their house" or "their flat" for raising and raising a family.

Figure 11: Selection of groups formed by the socio-technical and intersectional decision trees for the Global North and South for the (Co-)ownership of RE with clear positive and negative deviations from the overall average (Co-)ownership of RE. The horizontal scale corresponds to the proportion of people with RE (co-)ownership in the respective characteristic group (values in %). The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

Extreme Cases of (Co-)ownership of RE

The results from the perspective of capital theory

As assumed, the results show that economic capital plays a key role in renewable energy (co-)ownership. However, social and cultural capital also have a comparatively high explanatory power.

Especially in the Global South, ownership is strongly linked to financial and infrastructural access, with the lowest rates among women in Uganda and individuals lacking modern heating. This supports the idea that economic capital is a prerequisite for investment. Higher ownership rates among men in Nigeria and individuals with central heating or heat pumps indicate that financial stability and infrastructure access facilitate renewable energy adoption, reinforcing the importance of economic capital.

In the Global North, ownership is more diversified, with social and cultural capital playing a greater role. Women in Sweden and Poland report the lowest ownership rates, while older women with solar home systems and men in multi-person households show higher participation. This suggests that energy knowledge (cultural capital) and shared financial resources (social capital) influence ownership decisions. Additionally, men using alternative cooking technologies exhibit higher ownership rates, possibly linking energy engagement with decentralised energy participation.

Overall, the findings confirm that economic capital remains the strongest predictor of ownership, particularly in the Global South, where financial constraints and infrastructure access shape participation. In the Global North, social capital (household structure, shared investment) and cultural capital (energy engagement) play a larger role, supporting the idea that knowledge and networks facilitate ownership opportunities.

Energy sustainability capability

The Energy Sustainability Capability Index (ESCI) is a rather complex indicator of experiences of marginalisation regarding an individual's energy consumption, which is presumably influenced by a variety of factors. The index measures a person's perception of the extent to which they are able to manage their energy consumption efficiently and sustainably. As such, response behaviour might depend on:

- 1) the individual's desire to manage their energy consumption efficiently and sustainably,
- 2) their identification of certain forms of energy consumption as efficient and sustainable, and
- 3) their perceived ability to act on this desire by using the forms of consumption they have identified as efficient or sustainable.

The third dimension (perceived ability to implement sustainable consumption) is particularly relevant in the context of marginalisation. Here, the ESCI reflects structural disadvantages, as economically, socially, or infrastructurally marginalised groups often struggle to realise their aspirations for sustainable consumption. In this sense, the

lack of the self-perceived capability to manage the own energy consumption in accordance with one's values can be seen as an expression of cultural marginalization.

Due to its complexity, it can be assumed that the response behaviour in the ESCI is characterised by different types of capital in a rather balanced manner. Economic capital determines the financial scope for investments in energy-efficient technologies, meaning that low-income households, despite being environmentally aware, often face structural disadvantages. Cultural capital, particularly environmental awareness and sustainability-related norms, influences which forms of energy consumption are perceived as efficient or sustainable—a perception that varies depending on social milieu. Cultural or educational capital is also crucial in understanding the technical and economic aspects of sustainable energy use and making informed decisions. Social capital, in the form of networks and support structures, can facilitate access to information about funding programmes or alternative energy sources, thereby enhancing the perceived ability to implement sustainable consumption.

The multidimensional nature of the ESCI thus implies that response behaviour is shaped not only by objective opportunities but also by subjective perceptions and knowledge resources. These are, in turn, influenced by differing levels of capital. Consequently, the ESCI not only captures the ability to engage in sustainable energy consumption but also reflects the extent to which individuals experience alignment between their values and their actual consumption practices.

Country wise Gender Gaps in the ESCI

In Figure 12, the average values of the ESCI for men and women across the studied countries are displayed. A clear regional pattern emerges, with ESCI levels consistently higher in the Global South than in the Global North. This suggests that individuals in Kenya, Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa perceive themselves as being better able to manage their energy consumption efficiently and sustainably compared to those in the European countries examined.

Among the Global South nations, Kenya and Nigeria report the highest ESCI values, while Uganda and South Africa show slightly lower, yet still elevated scores. Among the Global North, Germany and Italy report the highest values among men, whereas among women, France ranks at the lower end, and among women, Poland.

Gender differences in ESCI are generally small across all examined countries, with men consistently reporting slightly higher values than women. The largest gender gaps (above the threshold $g < .1$) are found in Sweden ($g = .28$) and Germany ($g = .14$), whereas in Kenya, Nigeria, and Uganda, gender disparities are minimal, indicating a more balanced perception of energy management capability between men and women in these regions.

These findings suggest that ESCI is shaped more by regional than by gendered factors. While individuals in the Global South report significantly higher ESCI levels, gender differences remain relatively minor across all countries, with slightly larger gaps in some European nations but virtually no disparities in African countries.

Figure 12: Country wise Gender Gaps in the ESCI. Weighted descriptive means of ANOVA. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

The ten most important predictors of the ESCI

While access to energy infrastructure plays a key role in both the Global North and South in predicting the capability for sustainable energy consumption, its influence varies according to the pattern typical for this report, with structural constraints shaping energy sustainability more strongly in the South and a broader range of social and economic factors playing a role in the North.

Energy sources for heating, cooking, and electricity are among the most important predictors, but their effects differ regionally. In the Global South, main fuel for heating (48.0), main fuel for cooking (24.1), and main heating method (25.8) indicate that reliance on traditional energy sources limits the ability to engage in sustainable energy use. In the Global North, these same factors have lower importance (heating: 17.6, cooking: 8.9, heating method: 10.1), suggesting that while infrastructure matters, sustainability capability is also shaped by behavioural and regulatory factors.

Urbanity is a strong predictor, particularly in the Global South (25.3 vs. 13.8 in the North), suggesting that urban infrastructure provides greater opportunities for sustainable energy use. Household income perception is more relevant in the Global South

(14.0 vs. 5.4), indicating that financial capacity plays a stronger role in determining whether individuals can transition to sustainable energy sources. Household income in the context of the ESCI might reflect access to efficiency measures and cleaner technologies rather than outright investment. Age has a moderate effect, with a greater impact in the Global South (14.4 vs. 10.8), indicating that sustainable energy engagement increases with financial and social stability.

A Spearman correlation of 0.87 ($p < .001$) suggests stronger regional consistency. This indicates that sustainability capability is following clear structural patterns it is less shaped by region-specific policy frameworks and social norms.

Social factors play a significant role, particularly caregiving responsibilities (17.1 vs. 6.3) and living situation (17.1 vs. 7.1), which are more influential in the Global South. Gender identity is a stronger predictor in the Global South (3.1 vs. 1.2).

Compared to other indices, ESCI is distinct in its focus on the structural and behavioural factors that shape sustainable energy use. While the Energy Poverty Index measures deprivation and the EPSEI reflects agency, ESCI captures the intersection of energy access, financial capacity, and everyday energy behaviour.

Figure 13: Top 10 variables for predicting the ESCI in Global North and Global South plus Gender identity. Increase in Node Purity's of ESCI Random Forest Analysis. Cutoff after ten predictors dependent from Global North.

Extreme group analysis for the ESCI

The decision tree-based analysis of extreme deviations in the ESCI is shown in Figure 14. In the Global South, individuals in urban environments report higher ESCI scores

compared to those in semi-rural or rural settings. Among women, those living in very urban areas and not engaged in caregiving responsibilities exhibit higher sustainability capability. Conversely, women in semi-rural areas using fossil-based fuels (e.g., gasoline, diesel, biogas, coal, or lignite briquettes) report lower sustainability capability, suggesting that reliance on less sustainable fuels is linked to perceived constraints in energy management.

Among men, those in very urban environments with access to modern heating solutions (e.g., central heating, heat pumps, or manufactured cookstoves) score the highest, while those in semi-rural areas engaged in caregiving report lowest ESCI levels. Caregiving responsibilities appear to limit energy sustainability capability for both women and men.⁶

In the Global North, the lowest ESCI values are observed among women with mental health problems and those with no available information on their electricity source, suggesting that both mental well-being and energy knowledge impact perceived sustainability capability. Being not able to name the electricity source of one's household may indicate a lack of control over energy choices, particularly among younger individuals in rented accommodations.

Among men, younger individuals (aged 27 or less) using traditional space heaters or cookstoves report lower sustainability capability, while older men (married, divorced, or widowed) with access to heat pumps score above the regional average. Among women, those aged 51 or older using solar home systems report the highest ESCI values, indicating that older women with renewable energy access feel more capable of managing their energy sustainably.

Gendered patterns in ESCI vary by region. In the Global South, urban residence and modern heating access boost sustainability capability, while caregiving limits it for both genders. Women relying on fossil fuels report lower scores. In the Global North, mental health, energy knowledge, and household stability are more influential. Women with mental health issues or limited energy awareness score lower, while men benefit from stable living arrangements and modern heating. Older women with solar home systems report the highest ESCI. Overall, caregiving constrains ESCI in the South, while in the North, knowledge, well-being, and household stability matter more.

⁶ In view of the negative correlation between care responsibility and ESCI, the high ESCI value of men living in very urban areas who have care responsibility for more than 10 people is irritating. We have not interpreted the care responsibility of this group.

Figure 14: Selection of groups formed by the socio-technical and intersectional decision trees for the Global North and South for the ESCI with clear positive and negative deviations from the overall average ESCI. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

Extreme Cases of ESCI

The results from the perspective of capital theory

The analyses imply that a mix of economic, cultural, and social capital shapes energy sustainability capability.

In the Global South, economic capital is the primary determinant, as urban residents with modern heating access report higher ESCI, while those in semi-rural areas relying on fossil fuels score the lowest. Caregiving responsibilities further restrict ESCI, particularly for women, reinforcing that financial and social constraints limit sustainable energy practices.

In the Global North, cultural and social capital play a larger role. Energy knowledge and mental well-being strongly influence ESCI, with lower scores among women with mental health issues and those unaware of their electricity source. Meanwhile, older individuals with renewable energy access score highest, suggesting that energy literacy and stable living conditions enhance sustainability capability.

Overall, economic and social capital drives ESCI in the Global South, while cultural and social capital (energy knowledge, household stability) are more decisive in the Global North.

Eco-Anxiety

Eco-anxiety, defined as chronic fear of environmental doom (Clayton et al., 2017), has gained increasing attention as climate change intensifies and individuals face heightened uncertainty regarding environmental sustainability. Adapted from the Climate Change Anxiety Scale developed by Wu et al. (2023), eco-anxiety captures cognitive, emotional, and behavioural dimensions, encompassing cognitive distress, characterized by persistent worry and rumination about environmental crises, emotional distress, which includes feelings of sadness, anger, or helplessness in response to environmental degradation, and behavioural impact, leading to changes in lifestyle, consumption patterns, or activism driven by environmental concerns. A person's response behaviour is presumably determined by (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020; Ojala et al., 2021; Pihkala, 2020):

- 1) a person's personality and values, how sensitively a person perceives environmental degradation and how resiliently they deal with this change, and
- 2) experiences that a person has with their environment. These experiences are influenced by how a person is affected by environmental degradation (geographically, socio-economically). In turn, these experiences can occur in a shock-like manner (e.g. during heatwaves or catastrophic floods in the region of residence) or in small steps (e.g. through news in traditional and social media).

Eco-anxiety reflects energy marginalisation when individuals feel powerless in accessing or influencing sustainable energy transitions, particularly in energy-insecure and climate-vulnerable communities (Pihkala, 2020; Schlosberg & Collins, 2014). Limited access to affordable clean energy heightens eco-anxiety by increasing

dependence on high-cost, high-emission fossil fuels, exacerbating both environmental and psychological distress (Bouzarovski & Simcock, 2017; Middlemiss & Gillard, 2015). Additionally, exclusion from energy policies fosters disempowerment and alienation, reinforcing eco-anxiety as a lived experience shaped by systemic energy inequalities (Cunsolo & Ellis, 2018; Jenkins et al., 2016).

Cultural and educational capital likely exert the strongest effect on eco-anxiety, as increased awareness of environmental threats directly correlates with higher anxiety levels (Wu et al., 2023). While economic capital provides financial means to mitigate personal risks, it does not necessarily reduce eco-anxiety, as high-income individuals may experience cognitive dissonance due to their disproportionate environmental impact (Hulme, 2009). Social capital plays a moderating role, influencing how eco-anxiety is processed rather than its emergence—strong community networks can foster resilience, whereas social isolation may intensify distress (Berry et al., 2010). Thus, while all capital forms interact, cultural and educational capital appear to be the most direct drivers of eco-anxiety.

Country wise Gender Gaps in the Eco Anxiety Index

The mean values of the Eco-Anxiety Index for men and women across the examined countries are presented in Figure 15. Eco-anxiety varies across regions, with the index being more pronounced in all countries of the Global South, regardless of gender.

Within the Global North, France, Poland, Germany and Portugal show relatively similar levels of eco-anxiety between men and women, while Italy stands out with slightly higher mean values, and Sweden reports significantly lower levels overall. In the African countries examined, no clear differences emerge between individual nations.

No significant gender differences in eco-anxiety levels are observed in the Global North. However, in the African nations, Uganda ($g = .30$) and Kenya ($g = .16$) exhibit higher differences between men and women. This suggests that in these regions, environmental concerns may be more pressing for men, possibly due to socio-economic factors or direct exposure to climate-related challenges such as droughts.

In summary, eco-anxiety is consistently higher in the Global South than in the Global North. Gender differences are mostly insignificant, except in Uganda and Kenya, where men report slightly higher levels. This suggests that direct exposure to environmental risks may shape eco-anxiety more strongly in these regions.

Figure 15: Country wise Gender Gap in the Eco Anxiety Index. Weighted descriptive means of ANOVA. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

The ten most important predictors of the Eco Anxiety Index

While energy infrastructure influences eco-anxiety in both the Global North and South, additional social and psychological factors play a role, particularly in the South.

Energy sources for lighting, cooking, and heating are the strongest predictors, but their effects differ across regions. In the Global North, main lighting source (26.2), main fuel for cooking (21.9), and main fuel for heating (19.9) have the highest importance, suggesting that eco-anxiety is linked to energy dependency and concerns over sustainability. In the Global South, these factors are similarly influential (lighting: 23.1, cooking: 20.7, heating: 19.1), indicating a remarkable similarity in the predictors of eco-anxiety between Global North and South.

Correspondingly, a Spearman correlation of 0.92 ($p < .001$) indicates strong regional consistency in predictor importance between Global North and South. Eco-anxiety appears to be universally tied to perceived environmental threats and individual vulnerability.

Urbanity is a strong predictor, particularly in the Global South (16.0 vs. 6.2 in the North), indicating that exposure to environmental degradation in urban areas heightens eco-anxiety. Household income perception is more relevant in the Global South (7.3 vs. 3.8). Age is a significant predictor, with a stronger effect in the Global South (11.2 vs. 6.7), suggesting that younger individuals experience higher eco-anxiety, possibly due to heightened awareness of climate risks.

Social factors, particularly caregiving responsibilities (9.6 vs. 2.8) and living situation (11.5 vs. 4.8), are more influential in the Global South, suggesting that those responsible for dependents experience greater eco-anxiety. Gender identity has a stronger effect in the Global South (2.9 vs. 0.8) which might be tied to gendered emotional responses rather than structural barriers due to the highly psychological character of eco-anxiety.

Compared to other indices, Eco-Anxiety Index is distinct in capturing cognitive and emotional reactions to environmental issues rather than direct material conditions or behavioural engagement. While the Energy Poverty Index focuses on deprivation and ESCI on energy choices, Eco-Anxiety Index reflects how individuals internalize environmental risks. In comparison to the other outcomes, it is unusual that the technical aspects of energy consumption are an equally good predictor of eco-anxiety in both the Global North and the Global South.

Figure 16: Top 10 variables for predicting the Eco Anxiety Index in Global North and Global South plus Gender identity. Increase in Node Purity's of Eco Anxiety Index Random Forest Analysis. Cutoff after ten predictors dependent from Global North.

Extreme group analysis for the Eco-Anxiety Index

Figure 17 shows the decision tree-based analysis of extreme deviations in the Eco-Anxiety Index. In the Global South, lower eco-anxiety scores are found among individuals who have never been responsible for caregiving and those with no heating and/or electricity from the national grid in their household. This suggests that eco-anxiety may be lower in groups with fewer social and familial responsibilities, possibly

due to reduced direct concern over environmental risks affecting dependents. The lower eco-anxiety among people without heating could indicate a generally lower level of engagement with energy issues.

Conversely, eco-anxiety is considerably higher among individuals with caregiving responsibilities, particularly among women identifying as members of minority or racialized groups, and among men relying on diverse or non-grid energy sources such as dry cell batteries, solar lanterns, or biomass fuels. This pattern suggests that energy insecurity and caregiving responsibilities amplify environmental concerns, particularly when individuals are more directly engaged with non-traditional energy sources that may be less stable or sustainable.

In the Global North, eco-anxiety is generally lower, but certain groups report considerably higher distress. The lowest eco-anxiety levels are found among older men in Sweden and women connected to national grid electricity, indicating that stability in both energy access and life circumstances correlates with reduced environmental concern. In contrast, eco-anxiety is highest among individuals using off-grid electricity sources such as solar home systems, rechargeable batteries, or mini-grids, especially among women. Similarly, men aged 27 to 38 with caregiving responsibilities report higher eco-anxiety, suggesting that both energy insecurity and social responsibilities contribute to heightened environmental distress.

Across both regions, several trends emerge. Eco-anxiety is lower among those with stable energy access and fewer caregiving responsibilities, while it is higher among those with alternative or off-grid energy sources, as well as individuals who actively care for others. In the Global South, men and women with caregiving responsibilities and minority group identities report the highest eco-anxiety, whereas in the Global North, women with non-traditional electricity sources and younger men with caregiving duties experience the greatest environmental concern.

Overall, these findings suggest that eco-anxiety is shaped by a combination of energy access, caregiving roles, and social integration. In the Global South, energy insecurity and caregiving responsibilities appear to be key drivers of heightened environmental concern, while in the Global North, non-grid energy use and social obligations contribute to increased eco-anxiety.

Figure 17: Selection of groups formed by the socio-technical and intersectional decision trees for the Global North and South for the Eco Anxiety Index with clear positive and negative deviations from the overall average. The error indicators mark the 95% confidence interval.

Extreme Cases of Ecological Anxiety

The results from the perspective of capital theory

The findings suggest that economic and social capital play a crucial role in shaping eco-anxiety, rather than cultural capital. Energy insecurity, caregiving responsibilities,

and financial constraints emerge as key drivers, with high similarities between the Global North and South.

A first similarity between Global North and South is the negative correlation between caregiving duties and eco-anxiety. Contrary to the theoretical assumption at the beginning of this section, it cannot be shown here that greater social integration builds more resilience to eco-anxiety. Instead, the obligations associated with higher social capital appear to be reflected in higher eco-anxiety.

A second similarity between the Global North and the Global South is that eco-anxiety is lower among people who do not have access to heating or an electricity connection to the national grid. This pattern is difficult to categorize in terms of capital theory. These are groups of people who tend to consume energy passively and at a low threshold. In this sense, one could speak of infrastructural capital, as electricity is presumably seen as a self-evident good.

Conversely, eco-anxiety is highest among people with caregiving responsibilities, particularly minority or racialized women, and men who rely on off-grid energy sources such as solar lanterns and biomass fuels. Self-classification as a member of a minority group and, where appropriate, active engagement with alternative energy sources each require a specific level of educational capital.

SUMMARY OF RESULTS

After the results of the analysis for the five outcomes examined have been presented in more detail, they are summarised in this section.

Summary regarding country-wise Gender Gaps

Table 11 summarises the findings from the previous sections. Comparing data patterns across the five outcomes reveals that energy poverty—largely shaped by regional infrastructure and household income levels—is more widespread in the Global South. This disparity is likely driven by lower levels of economic capital in these regions.

Table 11: Content comparison of outcomes regarding country wise Gender Gaps.

Index	Comparison of Level in Global North and South	Comparison of Gender Gaps in Global North and South	Significant Gender Gaps by Country
Energy Poverty Index (EPI)	North > South: Energy poverty more prevalent in Global South.	No clear pattern.	Small effects in France, Portugal, and Sweden (men > women); Small effect in Kenya (men < women)
Energy Political Self-Efficacy Index (EPSEI)	North < South: Believe in individual energy political self-efficacy on average higher in Global South.	Men in all countries with higher energy political self-efficacy	Medium effects in France, Germany, Sweden, Poland, and Italy. In principle smaller effects in African countries.
Renewable Energy (Co-)Ownership Index	No clear pattern	In Global North, RE (co-)ownership is more prevalent among men.	Small effects in Sweden, Italy, and Germany (men > women)
Energy Sustainability Capability Index (ESCI)	North < South: Believe in capability for sustainable energy consumption on average higher in Global South	In all countries small to negligible gender gaps in favour of men.	Small effects in Sweden and Germany (men > women)
Eco-Anxiety Index (EAI)	North < South: Eco-Anxiety more prevalent in Global South	No gender gaps with two exemptions in Global South where men show higher values	Small effects in Uganda and Kenya (men > women)

Surprisingly, however, the proportion of individuals with RE (co-)ownership in the Global North is not substantially higher than in the Global South, despite financial investment capacity being a key predictor. This suggests that the transition to sustainable energy is not solely dependent on economic wealth. Local, small-scale energy solutions can also play a crucial role in expanding access to renewable energy.

In contrast to these economically driven factors, marginalisation experiences linked to energy citizenship, such as energy political self-efficacy (EPSEI) and energy sustainability capability (ESCI), appear more prevalent in the Global North. This may indicate

that individuals in the Global North are more engaged in reflecting on, questioning, and struggling with sustainable energy policies and consumption.

However, this pattern does not hold for eco-anxiety (EAI). Eco-anxiety is more widespread in the Global South, possibly due to its existential nature. While EPSEI and ESCI measure more secondary concerns (in terms of Maslow's hierarchy of needs), responses in the Eco-Anxiety Index are more closely linked to personal security and experiences of uncertainty.

The comparison of the five examined forms of energy marginalisation reveals a complex pattern of gender disparities. Men in all countries report higher levels of energy political self-efficacy (EPSEI), yet gender gaps in other areas are less consistent. In the Global North, men are slightly more likely to be (co-)owners of RE than women, whereas these gender disparities are largely absent in the Global South.

These findings suggest that energy marginalisation is not solely a matter of economic resources but that some of its aspects are also shaped by social and political structures. While energy poverty is primarily driven by infrastructure and economic conditions, gender gaps are most pronounced where access to political participation and entrepreneurial involvement in the energy sector is concerned.

Notably, gender differences in perceived energy sustainability capability (ESCI) remain minimal, indicating that men and women generally assess their ability to engage in sustainable energy consumption similarly, regardless of regional context. Similarly, eco-anxiety (EAI) does not exhibit consistent gender gaps, except in a few Global South countries. This suggests that environmental concerns are more closely linked to local uncertainties than to gender-specific factors.

The findings underline that gender gaps in the energy sector manifest differently across regions. In the Global North, structural barriers limiting women's access to renewable energy and political participation are of relevance, while in the Global South, gender disparities are less pronounced. These differences call for tailored policy responses.

In the Global North, policies should focus on increasing women's participation in energy policymaking and decision-making processes while promoting their involvement in renewable energy. Financial incentives, energy education programmes, and mentoring schemes can help reduce gender gaps in RE (co-)ownership and political self-efficacy. At the same time, sustainable energy solutions in the Global South must be made accessible both economically and socially, addressing both energy poverty and gender equality.

In summary, the analysis of the national gender gaps implies two key policy recommendation:

- Support programmes for women in bottom-up energy policymaking and renewable energy in the Global North.
- Gender-sensitive measures to combat energy poverty in the Global South.

Summary of most important predictors

Does the consideration of the most important predictors of the outcomes investigated imply specific intersectional gender aspects in experiences of marginalisation in the context of energy consumption and citizenship? Table 5 provides an overview over the importance of two exemplary technical and two social predictors for the five studied energy-related outcomes—energy poverty, political self-efficacy, renewable energy ownership, sustainability capability, and eco-anxiety—while also highlighting the role of gender in each case.

Table 12: Comparison of outcomes regarding the predictive importance of exemplary technical and social variables (IncNodePurity), and the role of gender identity. Higher values mean that a variable is used in many trees and plays an important role in automatic group formation in random forest analyses.

Index	Heating Fuel (North/South)	Cooking Fuel	Care Responsibility	Urbanity	Influence of Gender Identity
Energy Poverty Index (EPI)	12/66	10/61	5/28	10/57	Clearly higher in Global South
Energy Political Self-Efficacy Index (EPSEI)	12/25	10/19	6/8	7/18	Higher in Global South
Renewable Energy (Co-)Ownership Index	7/15	5/10	2/9	2/5	Minimal in both regions, financial resources determine ownership
Energy Sustainability Capability Index (ESCI)	18/48	9/24	14/25	6/17	Higher in Global South
Eco-Anxiety Index (EAI)	20/19	22/21	6/16	3/10	Higher in Global South

The comparative table conveys a few of the key insights from the analysis of the most important predictors of energy participation and marginalisation in a nutshell. According to this, the predictors outlined show the strongest explanatory power for energy poverty in the Global South. In terms of energy poverty, the Global North and South appear to be very dissimilar. In the Global South, energy poverty is much more pronounced and has a stronger infrastructural component. In the other types of marginalisation, the North and South are much more similar, especially in terms of eco-anxiety and energy political self-efficacy. In contrast, when considering the Global North, the predictors are most effective in explaining eco-anxiety. Here, the technical predictors have a similarly good explanatory power as in the Global South.

RE (co-)ownership is the most difficult to predict. This also seems surprising, as RE ownership can presumably also be expressed in very specific technical aspects of a household's energy consumption - e.g. in the heat pump or solar panel. Gender identity, as an isolated predictor, plays a comparatively minor role. The strongest impact of gender identity is observed in the Energy Poverty Index in the Global South, though even here, the identified technical and social predictors carry much greater explanatory power.

The analysis of key predictors of energy marginalisation leads to the following conclusions:

- In the Global South, marginalisation in energy consumption and citizenship is largely explained by energy availability and affordability (technical predictors).
- In the Global North, technical and social predictors have a more balanced influence on energy marginalisation.
- Gender identity plays a comparatively minor role in explaining energy-related marginalisation.

From this comparison, it can be inferred that gender studies might focus on the intersection between gender identity and disparities in fuel and electricity access, household income, and the degree of social integration of household members.

The findings highlight that energy marginalisation takes different forms in the Global North and Global South, requiring policies that address region-specific barriers. In the Global South, where energy poverty is shaped by infrastructure deficits and affordability constraints, the most effective policy measures include expanding energy access, subsidising clean energy, and implementing structural reforms. Universal electrification and reducing reliance on traditional fuels would directly target the strongest predictors of marginalisation.

By contrast, in the Global North, where social and behavioural factors play a greater role, marginalisation is less about access and more about energy engagement and affordability. Policies should focus on enhancing energy literacy, offering financial incentives for sustainable energy consumption, and ensuring more inclusive (requiring less energy literacy) access to affordable renewable energy, so that consumers can make informed choices and actively participate in the energy transition. To summarise the policy implications:

- Global South: Prioritise infrastructure expansion and affordability measures to address fundamental energy access barriers.

- Global North: Strengthen consumer education, financial accessibility, and behavioural incentives to encourage more inclusive energy engagement.
- Gender inclusion: Address economic disparities and promote gender-equitable decision-making in energy governance and household energy management.

Summary of Extreme Group Comparison

In the extreme group comparison conducted for each outcome, intersectional patterns were analysed in a narrower sense. This comparison provides insight into which factors contribute to men and women experiencing certain forms of energy marginalisation more intensely. Many of these factors are not inherently gender-specific. For instance, the likelihood of being a (co-)owner of a RE facility increases for both men and women when they live in a household shared with a partner or siblings. However, it is plausible that traditional gender roles shape how individuals relate to the facility—with men more likely to be decision-makers, providers, and maintainers of the RE facility, while women may act as co-decision-makers and users.

Table 13 presents the, in our view, clearest hypotheses that can be inferred from the extreme group analysis. To illustrate these patterns, the table also includes the groups in the Global North and South with the lowest mean values for each outcome.

Urbanity and education are key predictors in the Global South, while age and household structure play a greater role in the Global North. In Global North, the consolidation of a households appears to play an important role. This primarily refers to family households where adult members tend to be better socially integrated and benefit both psychologically and economically from shared resources and collective financial stability. We speak of consolidation because it is not the size of the household that seems to be decisive, but age and marital status. It seems plausible to assume that investments in RE systems or in the sustainability of energy consumption in the Global North only become attractive when a person expects to remain in a property in the long term.

Caregiving responsibilities are of high importance in both Global North and Global South. They have mixed effects—they enhance energy political self-efficacy, increase the likelihood of experiencing eco-anxiety, and limit sustainability capability.

Energy poverty appears less gendered, being primarily driven by infrastructure and affordability. Political self-efficacy is shaped more by education and social status than by national context. Renewable energy ownership is lowest among women, particularly those with limited access to energy information. Mental health issues reduce sustainability capability, especially among women in the Global North.

Table 13: Comparison table for the intersectional extreme case analyses. The table is very interpretative and its focus is on socio-demographic characteristics (not technical characteristics). Values for Eco-Anxiety Index are reversed (The two examples represent

Index	Global North: clear hypotheses	Global South: clear hypotheses	Group in Global North and South with lowest mean
Energy Poverty Index (EPI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The higher age, the lower energy poverty. • The national context has a considerable influence on energy poverty. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The higher urbanity, the lower energy poverty. • The national context has a considerable influence on energy poverty. 	<p>Global North, Man, Age 27 or younger, Religion: Muslim/Hindu/Jewish</p> <p>Global South, Man, Rural to semi-urban area, Uganda</p>
Energy Political Self-Efficacy Index (EPSEI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The higher education, the higher energy political self-efficacy. • If care responsibility, energy political self-efficacy is higher. • If no member of a minority group, energy political self-efficacy is higher. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If care responsibility, energy political self-efficacy is higher. • If no information on being member of a minority group, energy political self-efficacy is higher. 	<p>Global North, Woman, low education, no member of minority or racialized group.</p> <p>Global South, Woman, Co care responsibility, No information if identifying as member of a minority group</p>
Renewable Energy (Co-)Ownership Index	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If living in a joint household, (co-)ownership of RE is more probable. • The national context has a considerable influence on the probability for (co-)ownership of RE. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The higher education, the more probable is (co-)ownership of RE. • The national context has a considerable influence on the probability for (co-)ownership of RE. 	<p>Global North, Women, No information on electricity source, Poland</p> <p>Global South, Woman, Uganda, Age 32 - 35</p>
Energy Sustainability Capability Index (ESCI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If no mental health problems, capability for sustainable energy consumption is higher. • The higher age, the higher the capability for sustainable energy consumption. • The national context has a considerable influence on the probability for (co-)ownership of RE. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The higher urbanity, the higher the capability for sustainable energy consumption. • If care responsibility, capability for sustainable energy consumption is lower. 	<p>Global North, Woman, No information on source of electricity, Mental health problems</p> <p>Global South, Woman, Semi-rural-living environment, Heterosexual, South Africa</p>
Eco-Anxiety Index (EAI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The higher age, the lower eco-anxiety. • If care responsibility, eco-anxiety is higher. • The national context has a considerable influence on eco-anxiety. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If care responsibility, eco-anxiety is higher. • The national context has a considerable influence on eco-anxiety. 	<p>Global North, Man, Source of electricity: dry cell battery torch/rechargeable battery/solar lantern/no electricity, Lighting: Candle/open fire/battery powered flashlight/torch or lantern/solar power lantern or flashlight/gasoline-oil-biogas-lamp/missing</p> <p>Global South, Man, Electricity: dry cell battery torch/solar lantern, Heating with charcoal briquettes/piped natural gas/LPG-cooking gas/kerosine-paraffin/Biogas/woodchips/Coal/Lignite unprocessed/ Agricultural or crop residue/sawdust/Alcohol-ethanol/grass/straws/shrubs/corn crop</p>

A THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR UNDERSTANDING ENERGY MARGINALIZATION AND ITS GENDER ASPECTS

The primary aim of this report is to determine whether experiences of energy marginalisation are gendered and to identify intersectional patterns within these experiences.

The analyses indicate that gender roles play a considerable role in political participation, as measured by energy political self-efficacy. However, for other forms of energy marginalisation examined, different identity characteristics appear to be more influential. These characteristics shape the economic, social, and cultural resources that individuals seek and can access. While demand for and ownership of these resources are not explicitly gendered, they are indirectly influenced by gendered structural inequalities, such as the gender pay gap or the gender technology gap.

Table 2 provides an interpretative summary of the theoretical implications of the analysed data, illustrating how a household's capital resources correlate with different forms of energy marginalisation. The table distinguishes between economic, cultural, social, and infrastructural capital, showing whether these factors positively, negatively, or not clearly correlate with the probability of experiencing energy poverty, energy political self-efficacy, renewable energy (co-)ownership, sustainability capability, and eco-anxiety.

Table 14: Interpretative summary of the analysed data on the correlation between a household's capital resources and the probability of experiencing specific types of energy marginalisation.

Index	Economic Capital	Cultural Capital	Social Capital	Infrastructural Capital
Energy Poverty Index (EPI)	Household income (+), Modern cooking/heating (+)	-	-	Urbanity (+), Access to energy infrastructure (+)
Energy Political Self-Efficacy Index (EPSEI)	-	Education (+)	Care responsibility (+)	Urbanity (+), Use of decentralized energy solutions (+), Access to energy infrastructure (+)
Renewable Energy (Co-)Ownership Index	Household income (+), Modern cooking/heating (+)	Education (+), Self-perception as minority group member (+)	Multi-person households/consolidated households (+)	Use of decentralized energy solutions (+), Access to energy infrastructure (+/-)

Energy Sustainability Capability Index (ESCI)	Modern cooking/heating (+)	Mental health issues (-); Awareness about household energy (+)	Care responsibility (-), Consolidated households (+)	Urbanity (+), Use of decentralized energy solutions (+)
Eco-Anxiety Index (EAI)	-	Self-perception as minority group member (-)	Care responsibility (-)	Access to energy infrastructure (+), Use of decentralized energy solutions (+)

It should be emphasized in the table that, in contrast to the types of capital originally introduced, infrastructural capital has been added. Our results show that an urban infrastructure and, for example, a connection to the national electricity grid significantly improve participation in the energy system and protect against marginalisation experiences. This is an independent form of capital, as high-quality public services cannot be bought with individual capital, but must be provided by the community. Infrastructural capital is closely interwoven with the other types of capital from which it arises (e.g. due to a solidary community) and whose acquisition it favours (e.g. through public schools).

The table highlights distinct patterns in how different forms of capital influence energy marginalisation. Economic capital plays a crucial role in reducing energy poverty, mitigating eco-anxiety, and enhancing participation in renewable energy and sustainability, but it has no clear impact on political self-efficacy.

Cultural capital is particularly relevant for energy political self-efficacy, renewable energy ownership, and sustainability capability, emphasising the importance of energy knowledge and awareness in fostering active participation in energy decisions.

Social capital shows a mixed influence—while it supports energy political self-efficacy and renewable energy ownership, it has a negative correlation with eco-anxiety, indicating that care responsibilities increase vulnerability for climate related stress.

The results of this study also point to the prominent role of infrastructural capital. Urbanity and access to the electricity grid and other infrastructures significantly shape the experience of participation and marginalisation among consumers and citizens. The positive integration of people with decentralised energy solutions is also noteworthy—although at this point it must be determined whether these alternative supply concepts are based on necessity or interest.

As mentioned, the analyses in this report show that an individual's capital endowment is a key causal mediator between gender and participation in energy

consumption and citizenship. The distribution of economic, cultural, and social capital is not gender-neutral, shaping the participation and marginalisation experiences related to energy consumption and citizenship differently for men and women.

Economic Capital: Financial Barriers to Energy Participation

Women generally have less financial capital due to the gender pay gap and investment disparities (Toczek et al., 2021). This limits their ability to invest RE systems or energy-efficient technology, contributing to lower RE (co-)ownership. Additionally, women face more restrictive access to financial credit (Pavlova & Gvetadze, 2023), further reducing their capacity to transition to sustainable energy.

Cultural Capital: Knowledge Gaps and Environmental Awareness

Men are more likely to receive technical education in energy-related fields, reinforcing gendered divisions in energy decision-making (UNESCO, 2022). This contributes to lower energy political self-efficacy among women, particularly in the Global North, where technical expertise is key to policy engagement. However, women report higher environmental awareness (McCright & Xiao, 2014), which correlates with greater eco-anxiety, particularly when financial constraints prevent them from acting on sustainability concerns.

Social Capital: Caregiving and Energy Access

Women bear greater caregiving responsibilities, limiting their time and financial resources for energy transitions (Folbre, 2017). This might result in lower sustainability capability. At the same time, women and men with caregiving duties report higher eco-anxiety, reflecting concern over environmental risks affecting their dependents. However, caregiving is also associated with higher energy political self-efficacy, which requires more in-depth analyses.

With the condensed theory of energy marginalisation presented in Table 14, we directly tie in with the idea of the resource man according to Strengers (2022) presented at the beginning. Unequal capital distribution reinforces gender disparities in energy access and participation. Women face financial barriers to energy ownership, lower technical knowledge, and greater caregiving burdens, restricting their ability to engage in sustainable energy transitions. Our report shows that these types of economic, educational and social factors matter for gendered patterns in energy participation and citizenship - and are easily overlooked in highly aggregated statistical analyses without an intersectional perspective.

Bourdieu (2010) already stated that the different capital endowments of an individual can both empower and burden them. He argued this using the example of university lecturers. The distinctive cultural capital of this professional group opens up access to the upper middle class for its members. Within the upper bourgeoisie, it

requires significantly more effort in terms of economic capital from the academic upper class relative to their own income to participate in the typical status symbols and ingroup practices of the upper bourgeoisie.

Similarly, our data indicate that social and cultural capital in particular are double-edged swords. On the one hand, a high level of education strengthens the ability to shape one's own energy consumption sustainably or the feeling of energy policy self-efficacy, but it also sensitises people to injustices and presumably promotes interest in and demand for sustainable consumption patterns. This ambivalence of non-gender-neutral privileges, which enable comprehensive participation in energy consumption and citizenship, offers exciting starting points for further research.

TRANSFER: PERSONAS OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND ENERGY CITIZENSHIP

Although energy marginalisation is a very real phenomenon, writing and researching about it often remains very abstract. To better illustrate the intersectional patterns of energy marginalisation and energy citizenship identified in this report, we present four personas that reflect different combinations of economic, social, and cultural capital. These personas were compiled using ChatGPT 4o based on our energy capital theory and the extreme group analyses. They capture the structural inequalities shaping energy access, engagement, and sustainability across different regions.

Following the presentation of the four personas created related policy implications are presented.

Amina – The Struggling Energy Caregiver (Global South)

Economic Capital	Low	
Social Capital	Low (Caregiving responsibilities, but single mother)	
Cultural Capital	Low (Limited education)	
Infrastructural Capital	Low (Semi-rural area, Uganda)	
Marginalisation Experience	Energy poverty, high eco-anxiety, limited access to RE	
Energy citizenship	Low engagement due to financial and infrastructural constraints	

Amina, a 34-year-old single mother in a semi-rural area of Uganda, faces significant energy poverty. She relies on charcoal briquettes for cooking and has no access to stable electricity. Her caregiving responsibilities limit her ability to seek formal employment, making her dependent on informal work with irregular income. Her low cultural capital—limited education and awareness of alternative energy solutions—prevents her from engaging in energy efficiency programs. As a result, she experiences high eco-anxiety, knowing that energy insecurity negatively affects her children's well-being. Despite these challenges, Amina has potentially supportive social capital through her community networks, which provide informal energy-sharing arrangements.

Johan – The Energy Independent Professional (Global North)

Economic Capital	High	
Social Capital	Moderate (Stable family life)	
Cultural Capital	High (Technical knowledge, sustainability awareness)	
Infrastructural Capital	High (Germany)	
Marginalisation Experience	Minimal	
Energy citizenship	High engagement in policy and personal sustainability practices	

Johan, a 45-year-old engineer in Germany, is a co-owner of a RE production installation and has installed a solar home system. His high economic capital enables him to invest in sustainable energy solutions, while his strong cultural capital (education in an energy-related field) enhances his energy political self-efficacy. He actively engages in discussions on energy policies and regularly participates in public consultations. His social capital—while moderate—stems from professional networks that encourage knowledge-sharing about sustainable energy investments.

Sofia – The Disengaged Tenant (Global North)

Economic Capital	Low to Moderate	
Social Capital	Low (Few social networks)	
Cultural Capital	Low (Limited energy awareness)	
Infrastructural capital	High (Poland)	
Marginalisation Experience	Low political self-efficacy, limited RE access	
Energy citizenship	Passive consumer, excluded from policy participation	

Sofia, a 29-year-old single woman in Poland, rents a small apartment where she has no control over energy choices. She has little awareness of sustainable energy solutions and relies on traditional heating methods, which contribute to higher energy bills. Despite being environmentally concerned, her financial constraints prevent her from transitioning to more sustainable consumption. Additionally, her low energy political self-efficacy—shaped by her limited education and lack of engagement with policymaking—further deters her from advocating for changes. Without strong social networks, she struggles to access information on government subsidies for energy-efficient housing.

Kwame – The Off-Grid Innovator (Global South)

Economic Capital	Moderate	
Social Capital	High (Community-driven initiatives)	
Cultural Capital	High (Self-taught technical skills)	
Infrastructural Capital	Moderate (Semi-urban area, Nigeria)	
Marginalisation Experience	Institutional barriers to renewable energy expansion	
Energy citizenship	High engagement in decentralised energy solutions	

Kwame, a 38-year-old entrepreneur in Nigeria, lives in a peri-urban area where the national grid is unreliable. To counteract this, he has built a small solar panel system for his home and local business. His cultural capital—acquired through self-education in energy technologies—has allowed him to create local solutions independent of state infrastructure. His strong social capital enables him to organise community initiatives for energy sharing. However, despite his technical skills and proactive stance, he faces regulatory barriers that limit his ability to scale up renewable energy solutions.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS FOR CREDIBLE AND JUST ENERGY TRANSITION PATHWAYS

The challenges presented in this report—whether in terms of political participation, prosumer engagement, vulnerability to climate change, or simply energy consumption—highlight the need for tailored local and regional solutions, supported by supra-national and national regulatory frameworks that facilitate their development. A crucial aspect of this demand is the availability of disaggregated data by gender, economic status, ethnicity, religion, and country. Such intersectional data enhance our capacity to gain deeper insights and design tailor-made policies. But what does this mean in practice?

We propose a **citizen-centred approach** that defines regionally specific personas, as illustrated in the previous section. The gEneSys citizen survey dataset, combined with machine learning techniques, enables detailed national-level modelling of such personas. By leveraging disaggregated data, these personas can be used to identify key barriers to energy participation for different social groups and develop policy solutions that are both effective and equitable. This ability to capture and analyse nuanced social differences strengthens the evidence base for inclusive policy design.

Once these personas are established, policymakers might follow a Design Thinking process (Kurek et al., 2023). This means developing a deep understanding of the barriers limiting energy participation for each group and then formulating, implementing, evaluating, and continuously refining policy measures. But what does this look like in practice?

This approach can be exemplified by Amina, Johan, Sofia and Kwame. Which measures could (1) improve the transition to affordable clean energy, (2) promote the quality of life of the four personas and at the same time (3) have a realistic cost-benefit ratio for the state and the individual?

Amina: Making Clean Energy Affordable for Low-Income Households

For many people, the main barrier to using clean energy is simple: it costs too much upfront. This is especially true for low-income households in regions like Uganda, where people like Amina still rely on expensive, polluting fuels such as charcoal. Without access to reliable electricity, families struggle with high costs, health risks from smoke inhalation, and daily uncertainty about their energy supply.

To solve this, governments should provide financial support to help people switch to cleaner, more affordable energy sources. This can include:

- Subsidised solar home systems, which allow households to generate their own electricity without needing access to the national grid.

- Pay-as-you-go models, which let families pay for solar energy in small instalments instead of making a large upfront investment.
- Community solar projects, where groups of households share the costs and benefits of a local renewable energy system.

These solutions have already been proven effective in countries like Rwanda and Kenya, where solar mini-grids and clean cooking programs have helped many people escape energy poverty (Grimm et al., 2017; Wagner et al., 2021). Investing in these systems not only improves people's quality of life but also reduces long-term government costs by cutting reliance on fossil fuel subsidies and reducing health problems caused by air pollution.

Johan: Empowering Homeowners to Benefit from Renewable Energy

At the other end of the spectrum, some people already produce their own clean energy—but they struggle to make the most of it because of government regulations. Johan, for example, has installed solar panels on his home in Germany, but he can't always sell the extra energy he generates because of unclear policies and a lack of storage incentives.

To fix this, policymakers need to make clean energy investments more attractive and financially rewarding by:

- Providing fair compensation for surplus energy through stable feed-in tariffs, so households can sell electricity back to the grid at a predictable rate.
- Subsidising battery storage, allowing homeowners to store solar energy for use when they need it, instead of losing it when supply exceeds demand.
- Supporting peer-to-peer energy trading, where individuals can sell electricity directly to neighbours rather than depending on large utility companies.

Countries like the Netherlands have already introduced citizen energy cooperatives, where communities manage their own renewable energy production and distribution, increasing both energy independence and political participation (Georgarakis et al., 2021).

Sofia: Helping Renters Gain Control Over Their Energy Bills

Unlike homeowners, renters often have no say in how their homes use energy. Sofia, for example, lives in an apartment in Poland where her landlord controls energy decisions. She pays high electricity bills but can't switch to a cheaper, cleaner energy source because she doesn't own the property. Many renters face this problem,

known as the “split incentive”—where landlords have no reason to invest in energy efficiency because they don't pay the bills.

To fix this, governments might introduce rules and incentives that encourage landlords to make energy upgrades. This could include:

- Tax credits for landlords who improve insulation, upgrade appliances, or install solar panels—helping them save money while benefiting tenants.
- Stronger rental regulations that require landlords to meet minimum energy efficiency standards, ensuring that renters aren't stuck with outdated, high-cost systems.
- Community solar programs that allow renters to access clean energy without needing to install panels on their buildings.

These policies have already been successful in France and the UK, where regulations and financial incentives have led to widespread improvements in rental housing energy efficiency (Bird & Hernández, 2012).

Kwame: Supporting Small-Scale Energy Entrepreneurs

Some people don't just use energy—they create businesses that help others access it. Kwame, for example, runs a small business in Nigeria using solar energy. He has the skills and motivation to expand his clean energy solutions, but financial and legal barriers make it difficult for him to grow.

Governments can help small-scale energy entrepreneurs by:

- Providing low-interest loans or microfinance options, allowing small businesses to invest in renewable energy projects.
- Creating clear licensing frameworks that make it easier for individuals to sell clean energy legally.
- Encouraging public-private partnerships, where governments work with small businesses to expand decentralised energy access.

Research has shown that local, small-scale energy solutions are often more effective than large, centralised projects in providing reliable electricity to rural and peri-urban areas (Lamhamedi & de Vries, 2024; Nicolini, 2024).

Practical Steps for an Inclusive Energy Transition from EU perspective

These were just four examples of how a more comprehensive look at the realities of citizens' lives can enable smarter energy transition policies. A truly inclusive and

gender-sensitive energy transition policy must address the diverse realities of energy consumers and ensure that all citizens—regardless of income, housing status, or social roles—can benefit from clean energy. This requires moving beyond one-size-fits-all regulations and instead developing targeted, practical measures that tackle specific barriers faced by different groups.

A gender-sensitive approach must recognise the social inequalities embedded in energy access and decision-making. Women, who are often responsible for household energy management, need targeted financial support for clean cooking solutions and energy-efficient housing, ensuring they are not disproportionately burdened by rising energy costs. At the same time, policies should strengthen women's participation in energy governance and entrepreneurship, removing barriers that prevent them from engaging in RE markets. Recognising that eco-anxiety disproportionately affects those who feel powerless in the energy transition, policymakers must ensure greater citizen participation in energy decision-making, giving people a stake in shaping their energy future.

A successful energy transition must be financially sustainable, socially equitable, and politically inclusive. Governments can achieve this by balancing subsidies with progressive pricing, leveraging public-private partnerships to mobilise investments, and using citizen-driven policy design to continuously refine energy measures. By prioritising affordability, political empowerment, and gender equity, policymakers can ensure that Europe's transition to clean energy is not just effective but fair for all.

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ANNEX

Table 4.1.1: Gender Gaps in energy poverty index by country.

	<i>Men</i>	<i>Women</i>	<i>N(men)</i>	<i>SD(men)</i>	<i>CI (men)</i>	<i>N(women)</i>	<i>SD(women)</i>	<i>CI(women)</i>	<i>Hedges g</i>	<i>t-statistic</i>	<i>p value</i>
France	5,55	5,36	1449	1,23	0,06	1512	1,33	0,07	0,15	4,14	0,00
Germany	5,92	5,88	1493	1,14	0,06	1462	1,14	0,06	0,03	0,89	0,37
Italy	5,48	5,37	1469	1,17	0,06	1474	1,24	0,06	0,09	2,55	0,01
Poland	5,60	5,48	1471	1,23	0,06	1443	1,22	0,06	0,10	2,67	0,01
Portugal	5,62	5,47	1432	1,21	0,06	1555	1,23	0,06	0,12	3,32	0,00
Sweden	6,07	5,93	1507	1,05	0,05	1450	1,15	0,06	0,12	3,37	0,00
Kenya	4,90	5,10	1483	1,54	0,08	1513	1,47	0,07	-0,13	-3,52	0,00
Nigeria	4,98	5,01	1509	1,60	0,08	1484	1,59	0,08	-0,02	-0,59	0,55
Uganda	4,25	4,39	1574	1,77	0,09	925	1,79	0,12	-0,08	-1,85	0,06
South Africa	5,14	5,16	1464	1,40	0,07	1531	1,42	0,07	-0,01	-0,36	0,72

Table 4.1.2: Importance of Energy Poverty Index Predictors.

Variable	Global North	Global South	Difference (South - North)	Rank Global North	Rank Global South
Main fuel for heating	12,10	66,17	54,07	1	2
Main fuel for cooking	10,10	61,52	51,41	2	3
Main heating method	10,58	60,42	49,85	3	4
Urban living environment (1-7 scale)	10,01	56,49	46,47	4	5
Household income perception	9,17	52,38	43,21	5	7
RespondentAge	8,80	35,41	26,61	6	8
Relationship status	7,32	22,48	15,16	7	11
Living situation	5,63	32,14	26,52	8	9
Religious identity or world view	5,44	8,00	2,55	9	15
Main electricity source	5,22	68,73	63,50	10	1
Gender identity	1,15	6,06	4,91	18	19
Taking care of someone in need	4,87	28,21	23,34	11	10
Main lighting source	3,34	53,29	49,96	12	6
Consider yourself to have a disability	2,90	2,06	-0,84	13	20
Main cooking method	2,32	13,54	11,22	14	12
Education Level	2,32	13,18	10,87	15	13
Mental health problems diagnosis	2,09	6,57	4,48	16	16
Chronic illness or longstanding health problem	1,70	6,48	4,78	17	17
Responsible for taking care of someone	1,14	6,47	5,33	19	18
Heterosexual	1,02	0,00	-1,02	20	21
Identify as a member of an ethnic minority or racialized group	0,97	8,61	7,64	21	14
Asexual	0,04	0,00	-0,04	22	22
Bisexual	0,01	0,00	-0,01	23	23
Gay	0,00	0,00	0,00	24	24
Lesbian	0,00	0,00	0,00	25	25
Pansexual	0,00	0,00	0,00	26	26
Food/drink prepared with cookstove or similar device	0,00	0,00	0,00	27	27
Use heating device or fire	0,00	0,00	0,00	28	28
Use anything for lighting	0,00	0,00	0,00	29	29

Table 4.1.3: Extreme Cases of Energy Poverty Index.

Group	Energy Poverty Index	N	SD	CI
Global South, Woman, Rural to semi-urban area, Uganda	3,77	120	1,88	-0,34
Global South, Woman, Rural to semi-urban area, Cooking on three stone stove/open fire	3,67	156	1,69	-0,26
Global South, Man, Rural to semi-urban area, Uganda	3,49	180	1,56	-0,23
Global South, Man, Cooking on three stone stove/open fire, Heating with coal/lignite unprocessed	3,66	457	1,74	-0,16
Global South, Woman, Very urban area, Kenya/Nigeria/South Africa	5,57	1440	1,41	-0,07
Global South, Woman, Very urban area, central heating/ Heating with manufactured space heater	5,93	635	1,65	-0,13
Global South, Man, Very urban area, Nigeria	5,56	582	1,48	-0,12
Global South, Man, Cooking on electric or piped natural gas stove/electric stove , Very urban area	5,58	6698	1,47	-0,04
Global South: Overall average	4,88	11484	1,60	-0,03
Global North, Woman, France, age <=43	5,11	571	1,30	-0,11
Global North, Woman, Cooking on traditional/manufactured solid fuel stove/three stone stove/open fire, Electricity source no information/dry cell battery torch/electric generator/rechargeable battery/solar lantern/no electricity	4,96	624	1,39	-0,11
Global North, Man, Age 27 or younger, Religion: Muslim/Hindu/Jewish	4,74	121	1,24	-0,22
Global North, Man, Electricity through electric generator/local mini grid/rechargeable battery, Cooking on Biogas stove/traditional solid fuel stove/ liquid fuel stove	4,82	456	1,35	-0,12
Global North, Woman, Germany/Sweden/ Age 57 and older	6,25	1016	0,98	-0,06
Global North, Woman, Cooking on electric stove, Germany/Sweden	6,06	2487	1,07	-0,04
Global North, Man, Age older than 65, Germany/Sweden	6,42	517	0,81	-0,07
Global North, Man, Electricity through national grid connection, Germany/Sweden	6,24	2235	0,93	-0,04
Global North: Overall average	5,64	17715	1,21	-0,02

Table 4.2.1: Gender Gaps in EPSEI by country.

	Men	Women	N(men)	SD(men)	CI (men)	N(women)	SD(women)	CI(women)	Hedges g	t-statistic	p value
France	3,09	2,67	1437	0,88	0,05	1509	0,96	0,05	0,46	12,39	0,00
Germany	3,16	2,72	1497	0,89	0,05	1477	0,89	0,05	0,50	13,64	0,00
Italy	2,96	2,66	1473	0,93	0,05	1472	1,02	0,05	0,31	8,34	0,00
Poland	2,94	2,59	1469	0,91	0,05	1439	1,00	0,05	0,36	9,73	0,00
Portugal	2,97	2,69	1430	0,90	0,05	1544	0,96	0,05	0,30	8,11	0,00
Sweden	3,10	2,64	1514	0,83	0,04	1458	0,92	0,05	0,52	14,26	0,00
Kenya	3,37	3,17	1485	0,87	0,04	1513	0,89	0,04	0,22	6,01	0,00
Nigeria	3,66	3,43	1509	0,96	0,05	1479	1,02	0,05	0,24	6,43	0,00
Uganda	3,36	3,13	1573	1,03	0,05	920	1,09	0,07	0,22	5,19	0,00
South-Africa	5,14	5,16	1464	1,40	0,07	1531	1,42	0,07	-0,01	-0,36	0,72

Table 4.2.2: Importance of EPSEI predictors.

Variable	Global North	Global South	Difference (South - North)	Rank Global North	Rank Global South
Main fuel for heating	12,10	24,82	12,72	1	1
Main fuel for cooking	10,10	19,35	9,24	2	3
Main lighting source	7,67	16,52	8,85	3	5
Urban living environment (1-7 scale)	6,77	17,92	11,14	4	4
Taking care of someone in need	5,47	8,30	2,83	5	10
Main heating method	5,47	19,96	14,49	6	2
RespondentAge	4,61	10,16	5,55	7	8
Main cooking method	4,58	7,76	3,19	8	11
Main electricity source	4,06	13,72	9,65	9	6
Living situation	3,63	13,02	9,38	10	7
Household income perception	3,28	8,34	5,07	11	9
Relationship status	2,73	7,10	4,37	12	12
Religious identity or world view	2,03	4,16	2,14	13	14
Education Level	1,18	4,99	3,81	14	13
Identify as a member of an ethnic minority or racialized group	0,92	2,06	1,14	15	18
Consider yourself to have a disability	0,88	1,74	0,85	16	19
Mental health problems diagnosis	0,70	3,43	2,73	17	15
Chronic illness or longstanding health problem	0,58	1,50	0,92	18	20
Gender identity	0,51	2,18	1,67	19	16
Responsible for taking care of someone	0,43	2,11	1,68	20	17
Bisexual	0,27		-0,27	21	21
Heterosexual	0,08		-0,08	22	22
Asexual	0,02		-0,02	23	23
Use heating device or fire	0,00	0,00	0,00	24	24
Use anything for lighting	0,00	0,00	0,00	25	25
Food/drink prepared with cookstove or similar device	0,00	0,00	0,00	29	26
Pansexual	0,00		0,00	26	27
Lesbian	0,00		0,00	27	28
Gay	0,00		0,00	28	29

Table 4.2.3: Extreme cases of EPSEI.

Group	EPSEI	N	SD	CI
Global South, Woman, No care responsibility, No information if identifying as member of minority group	2,74	241	1,06	-0,13
Global South, Woman, Heating no information, No care responsibility	2,85	1387	0,96	-0,05
Global South, Man, No care responsibility, No information if identifying as member of minority group	2,97	250	1,13	-0,14
Global South, Man, Heating no information, i have been responsible for taking care of someone in need	3,07	727	0,97	-0,07
Global South, Woman, Care responsibility of 2 to 10 h/week, Very urban area	3,71	632	0,99	-0,08
Global South, Woman, Heating with central heating/heat pump, Care responsibility of 4 h/week or more	4,05	195	0,86	-0,12
Global South, Man, Care responsibility of 4 to 14h/week, Nigeria	3,94	433	0,89	-0,08
Global South, Man, Heating with heat pump, Very urban area	4,29	107	0,81	-0,15
Global South: Overall average	3,35	11469	0,99	-0,02
Global North, Woman, low education, no member of minority or racialized group	2,45	1168	0,99	-0,06
Global North, Woman, no info/ other source of electricity, low education	2,36	301	1,10	-0,12
Global North, Man, low education, no member of minority or racialized group	2,79	1087	0,94	-0,06
Global North, Man, low education, no member of minority or racialized group	2,79	1087	0,94	-0,06
Global North, Woman, high education, currently responsible for taking care of someone in need	3,07	961	0,96	-0,06
Global North, Woman, Electricity through Solar home system/electric generator, Current and past care responsibility	3,41	139	1,01	-0,17
Global North, Man, high education, Germany	3,39	629	0,89	-0,07
Global North, Man, high education, Movable Firepan/solar cooker/ manufactured solid fuel stove/Three stone stove/open fire	4,02	120	0,83	-0,15
Global North: Overall average	2,85	17717	0,95	-0,01

Table 4.3.1: Gender Gaps in (Co-)ownership of RE by country.

	Men	Women	N(men)	SD(men)	CI (men)	N(women)	SD(women)	CI(women)	Hedges g	t-statistic	p value
France	0,07	0,05	1412	0,26	0,01	1489	0,22	0,01	0,08	2,08	0,04
Germany	0,18	0,13	1456	0,38	0,02	1401	0,33	0,02	0,14	3,82	0,00
Italy	0,11	0,06	1424	0,31	0,02	1387	0,24	0,01	0,15	4,09	0,00
Poland	0,13	0,10	1432	0,34	0,02	1420	0,31	0,02	0,08	2,05	0,04
Portugal	0,09	0,06	1400	0,29	0,02	1494	0,25	0,01	0,10	2,65	0,01
Sweden	0,11	0,05	1451	0,32	0,02	1371	0,22	0,01	0,23	6,19	0,00
Kenya	0,11	0,10	1464	0,31	0,02	1452	0,30	0,02	0,04	1,03	0,30
Nigeria	0,17	0,13	1457	0,38	0,02	1456	0,34	0,02	0,12	3,11	0,00
Uganda	0,06	0,04	1521	0,24	0,01	879	0,20	0,01	0,08	1,81	0,07
South Africa	0,13	0,15	1425	0,33	0,02	1466	0,36	0,02	-0,06	-1,74	0,08

Table 4.3.2: Importance of (Co-)ownership of RE predictors.

Variable	Global North	Global South	Difference (South - North)	Rank Global North	Rank Global South
Main electricity source	12,15	7,08	-5,08	1	7
Main lighting source	9,28	7,38	-1,89	2	6
Main fuel for heating	6,86	14,81	7,95	3	1
Main fuel for cooking	5,22	9,56	4,34	4	4
Main heating method	3,75	10,04	6,29	5	3
RespondentAge	2,75	6,84	4,09	6	8
Identify as a member of an ethnic minority or racialized group	2,64	0,93	-1,71	7	18
Urban living environment (1-7 scale)	2,41	8,59	6,19	8	5
Religious identity or world view	1,96	1,17	-0,80	9	16
Taking care of someone in need	1,89	5,01	3,13	10	10
Living situation	1,55	5,02	3,47	11	9
Education Level	1,28	1,35	0,07	12	14
Consider yourself to have a disability	1,08	1,22	0,14	13	15
Household income perception	1,06	14,77	13,71	14	2
Relationship status	1,00	3,74	2,73	15	11
Main cooking method	0,83	2,22	1,39	16	12
Chronic illness or longstanding health problem	0,63	0,78	0,15	17	20
Responsible for taking care of someone	0,39	1,14	0,75	18	17
Mental health problems diagnosis	0,38	1,41	1,02	19	13
Gender identity	0,36	0,89	0,54	20	19
Heterosexual	0,01		-0,01	21	21
Bisexual	0,00		0,00	22	22
Asexual	0,00		0,00	23	23
Use heating device or fire	0,00	0,00	0,00	24	24
Use anything for lighting	0,00	0,00	0,00	25	25
Food/drink prepared with cookstove or similar device	0,00	0,00	0,00	26	26
Pansexual	0,00		0,00	27	27
Lesbian	0,00		0,00	28	28
Gay	0,00		0,00	29	29

Table 4.3.3: Extreme cases of (Co-)ownership of RE

Group	Energy Poverty Index	N
Global South, Woman, Uganda, Age 32 - 35	0	111
Global South, Woman, Heating no information, Electricity through national grid/local mini grid	2,6	1565
Global South, Man, Uganda, no member of minority or racialized group	3,5	925
Global South, Man, Heating no information, Electricity through national grid/local mini grid	4,1	2283
Global South, Woman, south africa, high education	21,7	826
Global South, Woman, Central heating/manufactured cookstove/heat pump/mobile heating pan, South africa	29,9	281
Global South, Man, Nigeria, mental health problems yes	32,1	224
Global South, Man, Heating with central heating/heatpump, high education	30,2	404
Global South: Overall average	11,1	11121
Global North, Women, Sweden, Not married	2,8	1005
Global North, Women, no information on Electricity source, Poland	1,4	139
Global North, Man, France, No information/not identifying as member of minority group	5,9	1281
Global North, Man, Electricity through dry cell battery/Torch/electric generator, no electricity household/local mini grid, no information on fuel energy source	4,9	162
Global North, Woman, Italy/Portugal, No information/not identifying as member of minority group	18,3	279
Global North, Woman, Electricity through solar home system, Age 38 and older	54,6	218
Global North, Man, Germany, living with partner and children/living with partners/siblings	31,1	444
Global North, Man, Electricity through national grid/other/no information, cooking with moveable firepan/solar cooker/three stone stove/open fire	39,6	106
Global North: Overall average	9,1	17137

Table 4.4.1: Gender Gaps in ESCI by country.

	Men	Women	N(men)	SD(men)	CI (men)	N(women)	SD(women)	CI(women)	Hedges g	t-statistic	p value
France	4,81	4,74	1444	1,15	0,06	1513	1,22	0,06	0,06	1,63	0,10
Germany	5,10	4,94	1487	1,14	0,06	1463	1,20	0,06	0,14	3,79	0,00
Italy	5,10	5,06	1475	1,10	0,06	1473	1,16	0,06	0,04	0,95	0,34
Poland	4,96	4,90	1467	1,18	0,06	1454	1,18	0,06	0,05	1,43	0,15
Portugal	4,94	4,83	1428	1,13	0,06	1551	1,19	0,06	0,09	2,46	0,01
Sweden	4,93	4,60	1509	1,14	0,06	1443	1,19	0,06	0,28	7,58	0,00
Kenya	5,61	5,59	1485	1,19	0,06	1513	1,17	0,06	0,02	0,44	0,66
Nigeria	5,59	5,57	1509	1,25	0,06	1485	1,23	0,06	0,02	0,56	0,58
Uganda	5,44	5,42	1576	1,30	0,06	926	1,28	0,08	0,02	0,40	0,69
South Africa	5,27	5,33	1462	1,18	0,06	1534	1,20	0,06	-0,04	-1,20	0,23

Table 4.4.2: Importance of ESCI predictors.

Variable	Global North	Global South	Difference (South - North)	Rank Global North	Rank Global South
Main fuel for heating	17,58	48,04	30,46	1	1
Urban living environment (1-7 scale)	13,81	25,35	11,54	2	4
RespondentAge	10,85	14,40	3,55	3	9
Main heating method	10,08	25,79	15,71	4	3
Main fuel for cooking	8,94	24,07	15,14	5	5
Living situation	7,06	17,06	10,01	6	8
Religious identity or world view	6,81	4,87	-1,95	7	14
Taking care of someone in need	6,34	17,09	10,75	8	7
Relationship status	6,30	9,86	3,56	9	11
Main electricity source	5,56	31,11	25,55	10	2
Household income perception	5,36	13,95	8,60	19	10
Main lighting source	4,60	19,53	14,93	11	6
Main cooking method	4,38	8,86	4,48	12	12
Mental health problems diagnosis	3,53	2,59	-0,94	13	19
Chronic illness or longstanding health problem	2,53	7,74	5,21	14	13
Education Level	2,32	4,70	2,38	15	15
Consider yourself to have a disability	1,83	1,70	-0,13	16	20
Responsible for taking care of someone	1,76	3,45	1,69	17	16
Gender Identity	1,23	3,12	1,89	18	18
Identify as a member of an ethnic minority or racialized group	1,02	3,29	2,27	20	17
Food/drink prepared with cookstove or similar device	0,16	0,00	-0,16	21	21
Heterosexual	0,16		-0,16	22	22
Asexual	0,04		-0,04	23	23
Bisexual	0,01		-0,01	24	24
Use heating device or fire	0,00	0,00	0,00	25	25
Use anything for lighting	0,00	0,00	0,00	26	26
Pansexual	0,00		0,00	27	27
Lesbian	0,00		0,00	28	28
Gay	0,00		0,00	29	29

Table 4.4.3: Extreme cases of ESCI.

Group	Energy Sustaina- bility Capability Index (ESCI)	N	SD	CI
Global South, Woman, Semi-rural living environment, Heterosexual	4,82	204	1,15	-0,16
Global South, Woman, Rural to semi-urban living environment,	4,97	652	1,34	-0,10
Global South, Man, semi-rural living environment, currently and has been responsible for taking care of someone in need	5,00	409	1,37	-0,13
Global South, Man, semi rural living environment, currently and has been responsible for taking care of someone in need	5,00	409	1,37	-0,13
Global South, Woman, Very urban living environment, not taking care of someone in need	5,97	1024	1,09	-0,07
Global South, Woman, Very urban living environment, heating with open fire/Three stone stove/central heating/heat pump/traditional cookstove/manufactured space heater/mobile heating pan	6,09	827	0,98	-0,07
Global South, Man, Very urban living environment, taking care of more than 10 peoples in need	6,16	162	0,97	-0,15
Global South, Man, Very urban living environment, central heating/manufactured cookstove/traditional cookstove/heat pump/manufactured space heater	6,14	641	0,99	-0,08
Global South: Overall average	5,48	11489	1,23	-0,02
Global North, Women, Sweden, mental health problems	4,50	738	1,20	-0,09
Global North, Woman, No information on source of electricity, mental health problems	4,36	284	1,24	-0,14
Global North, Man, Single/Dating in relationship/Co-Habiting, France Poland/Portugal/Sweden	4,80	2788	1,16	-0,04
Global North, Man, traditional space heater/traditional cookstove, age 27 or less	4,64	424	1,07	-0,10
Global North, Woman, Germany/Italy, age over 56	5,24	958	1,18	-0,07
Global North, Woman, source of electricity solar home system, age over 51	5,64	122	1,16	-0,21
Global North, Man, Married/Divorced/Widowed, Germany/Italy	5,23	1659	1,10	-0,05
Global North, Man, Heating with Heat pump, No mental health problems	5,34	612	1,02	-0,08
Global North: Overall average	4,90	17780	1,17	-0,02

Table 4.5.1: Gender Gaps in Eco-Anxiety Index by country.

	Men	Women	N(men)	SD(men)	CI (men)	N(women)	SD(women)	CI(women)	Hedges g	t-statistic	p value
France	1,98	1,91	1433	0,98	0,05	1515	0,95	0,05	0,07	1,86	0,06
Germany	1,97	1,88	1480	1,09	0,06	1468	0,97	0,05	0,08	2,17	0,03
Italy	2,23	2,22	1463	1,08	0,06	1469	1,08	0,06	0,01	0,17	0,86
Poland	2,05	2,09	1454	1,02	0,05	1427	1,04	0,05	-0,04	-1,14	0,25
Portugal	2,14	2,12	1426	0,99	0,05	1544	0,93	0,05	0,03	0,68	0,49
Sweden	1,71	1,71	1512	0,98	0,05	1436	0,89	0,05	0,00	0,08	0,94
Kenya	2,64	2,49	1483	0,97	0,05	1511	0,88	0,04	0,16	4,44	0,00
Nigeria	2,60	2,55	1507	1,01	0,05	1484	0,96	0,05	0,04	1,19	0,23
Uganda	2,71	2,42	1574	1,00	0,05	926	0,93	0,06	0,30	7,28	0,00
South Africa	2,47	2,47	1462	1,06	0,05	1528	1,00	0,05	0,00	0,03	0,97

Table 4.5.2: Importance of Eco-Anxiety Index predictors

Variable	Global North	Global South	Difference (South - North)	Rank Global North	Rank Global South
Main lighting source	26,24	23,13	-3,11	1	1
Main fuel for cooking	21,89	20,65	-1,24	2	2
Main fuel for heating	19,87	19,14	-0,73	3	3
Main heating method	14,25	17,04	2,79	4	5
Main cooking method	7,16	6,67	-0,49	5	12
RespondentAge	6,66	11,20	4,54	6	8
Main electricity source	6,37	17,38	11,02	7	4
Urban living environment (1-7 scale)	6,16	15,99	9,83	8	6
Living situation	4,76	11,54	6,78	9	7
Religious identity or world view	4,05	5,55	1,51	10	13
Household income perception	3,82	7,34	3,52	11	11
Relationship status	3,41	7,82	4,41	12	10
Taking care of someone in need	2,82	9,62	6,80	13	9
Education Level	1,54	2,68	1,14	14	16
Responsible for taking care of someone	1,08	2,54	1,46	15	17
Mental health problems diagnosis	1,02	1,95	0,93	16	18
Consider yourself to have a disability	0,87	0,82	-0,05	17	20
Gender identity	0,75	2,90	2,14	18	15
Identify as a member of an ethnic minority or racialized group	0,68	2,94	2,26	19	14
Chronic illness or longstanding health problem	0,47	1,73	1,26	20	19
Heterosexual	0,21		-0,21	21	21
Bisexual	0,13		-0,13	22	22
Use heating device or fire	0,02	0,00	-0,02	23	23
Asexual	0,00		0,00	24	24
Use anything for lighting	0,00	0,00	0,00	25	25
Food/drink prepared with cookstove or similar device	0,00	0,00	0,00	26	26
Pansexual	0,00		0,00	27	27
Lesbian	0,00		0,00	28	28
Gay	0,00		0,00	29	29

Table 4.5.3: Extreme cases of Eco-Anxiety Index

Group	Ecological anxiety	N	SD	CI
Global South, Woman, has never been responsible for taking care of someone in need	2,10	332	0,99	-0,11
Global South, Woman, no information on heating have never been responsible for taking care of someone in need	2,09	464	0,83	-0,08
Global South, Woman, never has been responsible for taking care of someone in need, no member of minority or racialized group	2,13	585	0,93	-0,08
Global South, Man, source of electricity national grid, never has been responsible for taking care of someone in need	2,10	622	0,94	-0,07
Global South, Woman, currently responsible for taking care of someone in need, not identifying as a member of minority or racialized group	2,68	657	1,04	-0,08
Global South, Woman, heating Manufactured cookstove/heat pump/traditional cookstive/mobile heating pan, identifying as a member of minority or racialized group	3,02	469	1,05	-0,09
Global South, Man, currently/ and has been responsible for taking care of someone in need	2,98	897	1,02	-0,07
Global South, Man, electricity: Dry cell battery torch/solar lantern, energy source: Charcoal briquettes/piped natural gas/LPG-cooking gas/kerosine-paraffin/Biogas/woodchips/Coal/Lignite unprocessed/ Agricultural or crop residue/sawdust/Alcohol-ethanol/grass/straws/shrubs/corn crop	3,44	122	0,99	-0,18
Global South: Overall average	2,55	11475	0,98	-0,02
Global North, Women, sweden, no muslim/Buddhist/missing	1,61	1401	0,80	-0,04
Global North, Woman, source of electricity: national grid/other, sweden	1,55	1093	0,72	-0,04
Global North, Man, older than 65, sweden	1,36	313	0,49	-0,05
Global North, Man, source of electricity: national grid, cooking: electric stove/other	1,66	3466	0,82	-0,03
Global North, Woman, Poland, no information or identifying as a member of minority or racialized group	2,60	220	1,17	-0,16
Global North, Woman, source of electricity: solar home system/electric generatot/local mini grid, lighting: open fire/rechargeable flashlight/mobile/torch or lantern/solar power lantern or flashlight/gasoline-oil-biogas-lamp	3,18	1430	1,10	-0,06
Global North: Man, age between 27 and 38, currently responsible and has been responsible in the past for taking care of someone in need	2,92	170	1,12	-0,17
Global North: Man, source of electricity: dry cell battery torch/rechargeable battery/solar lantern/no electricity, lighting: Candle/open fire/battery powered flashlight/torch or lantern/solar power lantern or flashlight/gasoline-oil-bio-gas-lamp/missing	3,45	173	0,91	-0,14
Global North: Overall average	2,00	17629	1,02	-0,01

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